

Bridging Gaps:

A Needs Assessment Report
for Enhanced Collaboration
Between Civilian and Defence
Cybersecurity Spheres

Authors

Université Libre de Brussels /
Solvay Business School

Georges Ataya, Palina Shauchuk, Ievgeniia
Lytvynova, Shafagh Kashef and Nicolas Ameye

Project	COcyber
Work Package	WP2 Coordination activities between cybersecurity civilian and defence spheres
Task	T2.2 Needs assessment and consultation for improved participation and collaboration
Submission date	29-01-2025

Abstract

This report summarises the Needs Assessment conducted under Task 2.2 of the COcyber project, focusing on identifying the needs, challenges, and opportunities for enhancing collaboration between the civilian and defence sectors in cybersecurity. As cyber threats evolve and become increasingly sophisticated, stronger partnerships between these sectors are essential to ensure national cyber resilience.

The primary objective of the assessment was to evaluate key areas for collaboration, including joint cyber defence initiatives, technology sharing, crisis management, and policy alignment. The study utilised a participatory approach, combining quantitative survey, qualitative focus group discussions, and consultations with key stakeholders, such as representatives from European institutions (ENISA, EDA, EC), national defence ministries, cybersecurity agencies, industrial players, and research institutions.

Key findings highlight critical gaps in collaboration and propose actionable insights to guide the development of a structured roadmap in Task 2.3. This roadmap aims to establish short-, medium-, and long-term strategies for fostering sustainable and integrated partnerships. The outcomes of this assessment provide a foundation for aligning civilian and defence efforts to address emerging cybersecurity challenges effectively.

Keywords

Cybersecurity Collaboration, Civilian Defence Partnership, Cyber Threat Landscape, Resilience and Response, Dual Use Technologies, Critical Infrastructure, Policy Harmonisation, Shared Intelligence, Governance Frameworks, Crisis Management, Public Private Partnerships, Incident Response, Innovation in Cyber Defence, Information Silos, Resource Allocation, Global Cooperation, Needs Assessment, Stakeholder Engagement, Focus Groups, Surveys.

Disclaimer

The COcyber project funded under Grant Agreement No. 101158606 is supported by the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre and funded by the European Union.

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Project funded by the European Commission in the Digital Europe Programme

Nature of the deliverable

R

Dissemination level

Public — fully open. e.g., website

✓

Sensitive (SEN) — limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement

EU classified — RESTREINT-UE/EU-RESTRICTED, CONFIDENTIEL-UE/EU-

CONFIDENTIAL, SECRET-UE/EU-SECRET under Decision 2015/444

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
ULB	Université Libre de Bruxelles Solvay Brussels School, COcyber partner leading Know-how, good practice sharing, and information transfer activities (WP4).
EU	European Union
MS	Member States
LR	Literature review
LRT	Literature review tool
BIT	Business Intelligence Tool
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
CCDCOE	NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence
GFCE	Global Forum on Cyber Expertise
ECYBRIDGE	ECYBRIDGE project
NIS2	Network and Information Systems
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
PESCO	Permanent Structured Cooperation
DIANA	Defence Innovation Accelerator for the North Atlantic
ECCC	European Cybersecurity Competence Centre
WP	Work Package
T	Task
EDA	European Defence Agency
EC	European Commission
VIP	Very Important Person
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
ISAC	Information Sharing and Analysis Centres

CSIRT	Computer Security Incident Response Teams
NCAF	National Cybersecurity Assessment Framework
IoT	Internet of Things
AI	Artificial Intelligence
APTs	Advanced Persistent Threats
PR	Press Release
NATO	North Atlantic Treaty Organisation
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
CYBERHEAD	Cybersecurity Higher Education Database
R&D	Research and Development
NCAF	National Cybersecurity Assessment Framework
CSIRTs	Computer Security Incident Response Teams

Executive Summary

This report defines the needs assessment and consultation framework for improving participation and collaboration within the cybersecurity domain. The primary aim is to identify coordination needs and set strategic directions for structured and sustainable engagement between civilian and defence cybersecurity spheres, as well as among COcyber community members and stakeholders in the short, medium, and long term.

The strategy is built upon four key areas that form the rationale for the COcyber coordination and support action:

Enhanced coordination is the first key area of the needs assessment. The analysis highlights the critical interdependencies between civilian and defence cybersecurity efforts. Through insights gathered from surveys, focus groups, and interviews, it became evident that improved coordination, information sharing, and technology transfer are essential to ensuring that advancements in one sphere benefit the other. These insights aim to create a more cohesive and responsive European cybersecurity landscape.

Stakeholder engagement is central to this strategy. Active participation and collaboration have been fostered among a wide range of stakeholders, including public and private cybersecurity actors, defence agencies, and diplomacy sectors. A stakeholder database of 451 relevant individuals was compiled, and valuable input was obtained from those who expressed interest in contributing. This participatory approach ensures that all relevant voices are heard and effectively integrated into the collaboration framework.

The project is committed to **strengthening mechanisms for exchange and coordination** between civilian and defence cybersecurity stakeholders. A series of consultations with European institutions, national defence ministries, agencies, industrial players, SMEs, and start-ups have addressed pressing collaboration challenges. These efforts, supported by data from surveys, focus groups, and interviews, inform actionable recommendations for future coordination activities.

Fostering synergies between ECYBRIDGE and COcyber is one of the focuses of the strategy. By aligning efforts, the projects aim to build a more integrated approach to cybersecurity across Europe. Joint planning and shared activities, aligned with Work Package (WP) 4, Task 4.2, are contributing to a unified approach to cybersecurity challenges.

This report lays the foundation for the COcyber roadmap and coordination activities with Task 2.3 of WP2, ensuring actionable outcomes that enhance collaboration, participation, and innovation in the European cybersecurity ecosystem.

1 Introduction

This report is part of the COcyber WP2, “Needs assessment and stakeholder consultation”. The main aim of WP2 is to identify the coordination needs and set strategic directions for fostering structured and sustainable collaboration between civilian and defence cybersecurity spheres, as well as among COcyber community members and stakeholders. The specific objectives are to:

- **Conduct a comprehensive needs assessment** using qualitative and quantitative methods, such as surveys, focus groups, and interviews, to gather insights from stakeholders in the cybersecurity, defence, and diplomacy sectors.
- **Establish feedback loops** with experts and advisors from relevant European institutions and agencies, including ENISA, the European Defence Agency (EDA), and the European Commission, to ensure alignment with EU priorities.
- **Organise consultations** with key stakeholders, including the EC, national defence ministries, industrial players, SMEs, start-ups, and other actors, to discuss urgent collaboration issues and foster stronger partnerships.
- **Provide input for the COcyber roadmap** (Task 2.3) by analysing stakeholder needs and shaping actionable recommendations to enhance participation and collaboration.

In this context, this report outlines the participatory approach used to identify coordination needs and address challenges in civilian–defence collaboration. It details the methods used for data collection, presents findings from stakeholder engagements, and highlights strategies for improving exchange and coordination across the cybersecurity ecosystem. Additionally, it explores synergies with related projects like ECYBRIDGE to amplify the impact of COcyber activities and ensure long-term sustainability. This document serves as a foundation for developing the COcyber roadmap and coordination activities (T2.3), contributing to a cohesive and responsive European cybersecurity landscape.

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1.1 Structure of the report

The report consists of four sections, all of which are interrelated, with each contributing to fostering the impact and sustainability of the COcyber project:

- **Section 1** shares information about related tasks and deliverables, general details about the report, technical specifications, study questions, and methodology.
- **Section 2** introduces the rationale for strengthened collaboration, focusing on key areas that require closer collaboration; presents the results of the literature review and COcyber stakeholders' opinions based on focus groups, interviews, and surveys addressing reasons to enhance collaboration and exploring ways to enhance collaboration.
- **Section 3** shares recommendations as the foundation for developing the COcyber roadmap and coordination activities (T2.3).
- **Section 4** provides the conclusions and outlines the next steps for the project's impact activities.

1.2. Related tasks and deliverables

This deliverable, offering an overarching strategy for addressing coordination needs and setting strategic directions to foster structured and sustainable collaboration between civilian and defence cybersecurity spheres, is published as part of the WP2 tasks. It is related to the following tasks and deliverables:

- T2.3: Roadmap & coordination activities
- T3.1: Cybersecurity Observatory
- T3.2: COcyber Platform development
- T3.3: COcyber Platform integrations
- T4.1: Best practices and case studies for enhanced cooperation between the two cybersecurity communities
- T4.2: Exchange of know-how and information-sharing activities
- T5.4: COcyber stakeholder engagement and Ambassador Programme
- T6.1: Synergies with existing initiatives
- T6.3: Sustainability strategy and activities

In alignment with these tasks, the report will contribute to and impact forthcoming deliverables under WPs 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6, including:

- D2.3: COcyber roadmap and activity report (M12, EOS)
- D3.1: Interactive online map of the EU cybersecurity landscape (M8, ULB)
- D3.3: COcyber Platform (M12, LC)
- D3.4: Report on the COcyber Platform integrations (M12, LC)
- D4.1: Guidelines on cybersecurity civil-defence cooperation (M15, ULB)
- D4.2: National case studies booklet on cybersecurity technology and information transfer (M17, ULB)
- D4.3: Toolkit for the organisation of know-how and information activities (M12, LC)
- D5.2: COcyber Hackathon (M11, EITD)
- D5.5: Project final conference (M24, LC)
- D6.1: Report on synergies with relevant cybersecurity initiatives and projects (M12, AMETIC)
- D6.3: COcyber sustainability plan (M12, AMETIC)

In addition, this report is closely linked to all other WPs and tasks, as it outlines the strategy for addressing coordination needs and setting strategic directions for fostering structured and sustainable collaboration between civilian and defence cybersecurity spheres. Collaboration among WP2, 3, 4, 5, and 6 will be especially close, as these WPs focus on ensuring the proper exploitation of COcyber results and outputs during and after the project, preparing for the long-term sustainability of the achieved results, and fostering synergies with existing relevant cybersecurity initiatives.

Finally, this report serves as the foundation for WP2, "Coordination activities between cybersecurity civilian and defence spheres," and specifically for Task 2.3, "Roadmap & coordination activities." The insights and recommendations outlined here will directly inform and shape the development of the roadmap and coordination activities, ensuring a strategic and well-aligned approach to fostering collaboration within the cybersecurity ecosystem.

1.3 Synopsis of the current cybersecurity landscape and the need for collaboration

The twenty-first century's digital revolution has opened unprecedented opportunities for innovation, economic growth, and improved services. Yet, this technological surge has also introduced an increasingly complex array of cyber threats. No longer limited to isolated hackers, adversaries now include well-funded, highly skilled cybercriminals, hacktivist groups, and nation-state actors wielding sophisticated digital weaponry. As these malicious actors' target information networks, critical infrastructure, and governmental services, it has become evident that defending the digital domain requires more than conventional, siloed responses.

Civilian and defence cybersecurity spheres have traditionally operated in parallel but separate tracks. The civilian sector, encompassing governmental agencies, public utilities, private industry, and non-profit entities, has focused on securing data privacy, intellectual property, consumer protection, and continuity of essential services. In contrast, defence establishments have concentrated on safeguarding national security assets, military communication channels, defence industrial bases, and strategic command-and-control systems.

With the threat landscape evolving at a rapid pace, this division no longer serves the best interests of national cyber resilience. Attacks today frequently cross the boundaries between civilian and defence targets, exploiting the weakest links in complex supply chains, shared infrastructures, and dual-use technologies. The complexity and interdependence of modern networks mean that a compromise in one sector can have catastrophic cascading effects in another. To meet these challenges, a closer, more integrated collaboration between civilian and defence cybersecurity spheres is urgently needed.

Drawing upon insights from the COCyber project and related stakeholder input, this report identifies key areas where improved cooperation can yield substantial benefits. It then proposes a phased approach—spanning short-, medium-, and long-term horizons—to create a robust, sustainable, and forward-looking cybersecurity ecosystem. By aligning policies, sharing information, developing a skilled workforce, harmonising frameworks, fostering innovation, and bridging cultural divides, both the civilian and defence sectors can strengthen their collective ability to deter, detect, and respond to cyber threats.

The ultimate goal is to move beyond ad-hoc coordination toward a mature, institutionalised partnership that leverages each sector's strengths. Such a partnership ensures that national cybersecurity efforts are resilient, adaptable, and prepared to counter the full spectrum of current and future cyber threats.

1.4 Technical specifications

The objective of this study is to assess the needs for improved collaboration between civilian and defence cybersecurity sectors, providing actionable insights into how such collaboration can enhance resilience, coordination, and efficiency in addressing evolving cyber threats. The study aims to uncover gaps, challenges, and opportunities for joint initiatives, technology sharing, policy harmonisation, and coordinated crisis management.

The study focuses on examining collaboration efforts across several dimensions, including governance structures, information-sharing mechanisms, joint cybersecurity training programs, and the development of dual-use technologies. Special attention is given to the interdependencies between civilian and defence infrastructures, highlighting the critical need for integration to counter increasingly sophisticated cyber threats.

To achieve these goals, the study employs a participatory approach, leveraging stakeholder consultations, quantitative surveys, and qualitative focus group discussions. The targeted participants include representatives from European institutions, national defence ministries, cybersecurity agencies, industrial players, SMEs, start-ups, and research organisations. The assessment addresses short-, medium-, and long-term objectives, ensuring a roadmap for structured and sustainable collaboration.

This study will serve as a foundational step in developing the COcyber roadmap (T2.3), offering strategic planning for enhanced cooperation and contributing to the creation of a more robust, adaptive, and cohesive European cybersecurity ecosystem.

1.4.1 Study questions

- Which key reasons and motivations drive the need for enhanced collaboration, and how are they prioritised across different sectors and regions?
- How can specific approaches be effectively implemented in the short, medium, and long term?
- How do different stakeholder groups (e.g., government agencies, private sector, academia, and international organisations) perceive the urgency of addressing these challenges, and what roles can they play in driving solutions?

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The complete set of questions can be found in **Appendix 1. Questionnaire**, **Appendix 4. Focus Group presentation** and **Appendix 5. Interview questionnaire**. Those Appendices provide a comprehensive overview of the questions designed to gather insights from stakeholders. It includes sections on collaboration challenges, priority-setting for cybersecurity initiatives, and suggestions for improving partnerships between civilian and defence sectors.

1.4.2 Methodology

The methodology for Task 2.2 adopts a participatory approach that integrates qualitative and quantitative methods with structured stakeholder engagement. This section outlines the approach for conducting a thorough stakeholder analysis to support our research objectives. By assessing stakeholder groups' importance, influence, and roles across three data collection streams—Focus Groups, Very Important Person (VIP) Interviews, and Surveys—we create a targeted engagement strategy that promotes meaningful collaboration and actionable insights.

Qualitative analysis was conducted through in-depth literature analysis, interviews and focus groups, providing deep insights from key stakeholders. Quantitative analysis was supported by survey data, capturing a wider range of perspectives. Feedback loops with European institutions were incorporated to ensure the research remains relevant and aligned with broader cybersecurity policies. This methodological framework guarantees that the task meets the needs of diverse stakeholders while fostering long-term collaboration between the civilian and defence sectors in cybersecurity.

Methodological note

To address the primary question of WP2 on needs assessment, the first step involved conducting an in-depth literature review. This review serves as a foundation for understanding existing research, frameworks, and best practices in cybersecurity collaboration between civilian and defence sectors.

Building on these insights, a comprehensive three-pronged approach has been developed, including Stream 1 – Focus Groups, Stream 2 – VIP Interviews, and Stream 3 – Survey. This methodology ensures that all relevant aspects are captured while incorporating the perspectives of diverse stakeholders. By integrating findings from the literature review with qualitative and quantitative data collection, this approach provides a holistic overview of cybersecurity needs. It facilitates the analysis of existing gaps, challenges, and opportunities for collaboration.

Literature review analysis

The literature analysis served as the foundation of this study, aiming to identify the most relevant publications and present their insights in a structured manner. The approach adopted involved:

- Mapping the needs for collaboration between civilian and defence cybersecurity sectors.
- Developing a search protocol to systematically identify sources and select relevant information.
- Creating the Literature Review Tool, an Excel-based framework designed to categorise information relevant to the research objectives.

The literature review process followed a structured three-step approach:

Step 1 – Identifying literature sources

To ensure a comprehensive review, the following sources were considered:

- Academic databases: Google Scholar and Web of Science, as key citation analysis sources.
- Industry and government reports: Publications from universities, cybersecurity firms, and governmental bodies.
- Reputable news sources: A selection of quality newspapers (e.g., The Times, The Economist, Financial Times, Le Monde).

Step 2 – Selecting and applying keywords

A predefined set of keywords was used for systematic searches across the selected sources. These included:

cybersecurity collaboration, public-private partnership, civil-military cooperation, threat intelligence exchange, cyber resilience, cyber threat mitigation, incident response coordination, cyber defence strategy, security operations centers, joint cyber exercises, among others.

Step 3 – Defining the publication period

- Scientific and academic literature was included without time restrictions.
- Industry and policy reports were considered from 2014/2015 onward to ensure relevance to current cybersecurity challenges.

As a result of this systematic review, a total of 338 academic papers, reports, and books were gathered, comprising:

- 100 works on cybersecurity and defence
- 147 works on civilian cybersecurity
- 91 works on dual-use cybersecurity
- Additionally, 54 frameworks and 67 case studies were identified for SWOT analysis.

Further details and insights from the **Literature Review Tool** can be found in **Appendix 9 Literature Review Tool**.

Stakeholder analysis

Stakeholder analysis is foundational to achieving strategic alignment, fostering collaboration, and ensuring that projects like cybersecurity collaboration between civilian and defence sectors are well-informed, inclusive, and impactful.

To organise and prioritise stakeholder engagement, we employed an Importance and Influence Matrix. This matrix categorises stakeholders into four groups based on their relevance to the project and ability to influence outcomes:

- **Group 1 (High Importance / Low Influence):** Civil society and end users, directly affected but with limited influence.
- **Group 2 (High Importance / High Influence):** Defence organisations, regulators and industry private sector representatives who are crucial to project success.
- **Group 3 (Low Importance / Low Influence):** Peripheral stakeholders such as certain academic and research institutions.
- **Group 4 (Low Importance / High Influence):** Industry SMEs representatives, influential but less directly engaged.

Stakeholder Group	Importance (Scale of 1 to 5)	Influence (Scale of 1 to 5)	Stakeholder Matrix Position
International and Defence Organisation Representatives	5	5	High Importance / High Influence (Group 2): (significant interest and influence). We involve these stakeholders heavily in the project; they are key to successful project outcomes.
Industry Private Sectors	4	4	High Importance / High Influence (Group 2): without deep involvement.

Regulators	4	5	High Importance / High Influence (Group 2): (significant interest and influence). We involve these stakeholders heavily in the project; they are key to successful project outcomes.
Academia and Research Institutions	2	2	Low Importance / Low Influence (Group 3): Less involved groups, we are interested in them but peripheral. Engage them lightly.
Civil Society and End Users	4	2	High Importance / Low Influence (Group 1): (often directly affected but less influential). We engage them to ensure project needs are met and to gain insights.

Table 1 Stakeholder Analysis (for three streams)

Source: own elaboration¹

¹ Full contact list of contacted organisations can be found in **Appendix 7. Stakeholders**.

With the help of the Engagement Ladder tool, we managed to clarify the level of interaction with each stakeholder group:

- **Purpose:** Categorise engagement from low to high involvement, helping decide how to interact with each stakeholder.
- **Application:** Place stakeholders along a ladder to guide the depth of their engagement:

By positioning each group within this matrix, we define their roles and establish the appropriate depth of engagement through the following strategies:

Engagement Level	Stakeholders	Engagement Type
Inform	Civil Society, academia, Broad COcyber Community	General updates for peripheral stakeholders for low engagement
Consult	SMEs, Industry	Regular surveys and targeted interactions for moderately involved groups
Involve	Regulators, Defence Organisations	Active participation in focus groups for high-priority stakeholders with high Involvement
Collaborate	Key Advisors, ENISA, EDA	high-level collaboration through VIP interviews for critical partners. With highest involvement

Table 2 Stakeholder Engagement Ladder

Three-pronged methodological framework and its implementation

Stream 1 “Focus groups”

Stream 1 focuses on in-depth data collection through focus groups, primarily involving the COcyber advisory board, COcyber partners, ENISA, EDA, and EC, as well as key groups from sectors such as defence, industry, and regulators. This stream required additional time for the organisation to ensure thorough feedback from a carefully selected group of stakeholders, with each group focusing on key topics related to future collaboration and strategic planning. The focus groups were held in late November and beginning of January, with scheduling largely dependent on participant availability.

Specific audiences were identified through the networks of ULB, EIT Digital, and EOS, which provided access to a diverse range of relevant professionals and experts in the field of cybersecurity. To ensure a well-rounded and insightful discussion, the contacts were organised into **four** distinct groups based on their roles, experience, and relevance to the project.

Priority was given to selecting candidates with specialised knowledge or experience that aligned with the key topics and goals of the focus groups and the project itself. This process allowed us to ensure that

each group contained individuals with a range of perspectives, enabling us to capture the most valuable insights to inform our needs assessment.

In the table below, an overview of the four groups is provided, along with a list of organisations that the participants were associated with, including both those we contacted and those who attended the focus group sessions.

Focus Groups (FG)	N of contacted organisations	N of responded Organisations	N of people attended the FG	Date of the event
Industry SMEs Focus Group	452	3	3	9 December 2024
Industry PS Focus Group		6	7	9 December 2024
Regulators Focus Group		5	5	11 December 2024
Defence Focus Group		1	0	The group was not formed due to only one participant. The invitations were sent to form a defence focus group; however, not enough responses were received. To address this gap, interviews were conducted with defence representatives to gather relevant insights.

Table 3 Focus Group

For each group, we developed a tailored email invitation (an example of which is provided in **Appendix 2. Emails invitations**). In addition, we reached out to several individuals via LinkedIn, using a personalised message referencing the project page to increase the response rate (a sample of this message can also be found in **Appendix 3. LinkedIn Invitations**).

The duration of each focus group was approximately 1.5 hours. A presentation, along with relevant questions (based on the literature review and desk research), was prepared for the participants (please refer to **Appendix 4. Focus Group presentation** for the presentation developed and shared with the participants). Each session was recorded, and detailed minutes were taken afterwards. The gathered information was analysed and incorporated into the needs assessment report.

Stream 2 VIP interviews

Stream 2 focused on interviewing senior executives from national defence ministries, national authorities, and key industry players, especially those with existing connections in the cybersecurity sector. These interviews allowed for detailed discussions on collaboration opportunities and practical needs within the civilian and defence spheres. The relationships with stakeholders in this stream is essential for understanding the broader strategic alignment and goals of the project. The challenges of coordinating suitable times with VIPs in this field are acknowledged, with the interview scheduling process taking approximately four months. In total, six interviews were successfully conducted across six organisations. The interview questionnaire is provided in **Appendix 5. Interview questionnaire**. The questionnaire is based on the literature review and desk research and is aligned with the questions related to the Focus group stream. Each interview lasted approximately 60–90 minutes, and participants provided informed consent prior to the interviews. Discussions were recorded (with consent) to ensure accuracy and supplemented with detailed field notes taken during the interviews. The collected interview data were transcribed and subjected to the analysis. This involved coding the responses to identify recurring themes, insights, and patterns. Findings were triangulated with data from other research streams (e.g., focus groups and survey) to ensure consistency and comprehensiveness.

Stream 3 Survey

Stream 3 involved a large-scale survey that focused on a broader, less formal audience, including members of the COcyber community and a diverse range of external stakeholders. To ensure the survey was conducted effectively and yielded meaningful results, a structured approach was designed to maximise the success rate. Below are the five steps that were undertaken:

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In **Step 1**, survey's objectives were defined, ensuring alignment with the overall goals of the project:

- Objective 1: Understand the rationale behind why collaboration between civilian and defence sectors is crucial, with a focus on current challenges and opportunities.
- Objective 2: Explore the methods and practical steps that can enhance collaboration, draw on specific ideas for joint projects, technology sharing, and governance structures.
- Objective 3: Dive deeper into future collaboration goals of cross-sector partnerships.

The survey aimed to:

- Understand the current challenges and opportunities in collaboration between civilian and defence cybersecurity sectors.
- Identify the key factors driving the need for strengthened collaboration.
- Explore actionable strategies for short-, medium-, and long-term improvements in cross-sector partnerships.
- Based on these objectives, we believe the survey not only supports the project goals but also complements and enhances the insights from the two other data collection streams.

In **Step 2**, using the stakeholder analysis conducted earlier, we identified the targeted audience groups for the survey. These groups included representatives from civilian and defence sectors, policymakers, industry experts, and other relevant stakeholders involved in cybersecurity.

Step 3 included the survey design focused on creating concise, relevant, and unbiased questions aligned with the objectives. A total of 9 questions were developed and grouped into three primary pillars:

- Why: Understanding the rationale and benefits of strengthening collaboration between civilian and defence cybersecurity spheres.
- How: Exploring actionable strategies for enhancing collaboration between the two sectors.
- Future Goals: Identifying long-term objectives for cross-sector partnerships in cybersecurity.

To ensure a comprehensive approach, the questionnaire included a mix of question types, such as multiple-choice, Likert scale, and open-ended questions, to capture both qualitative and quantitative data. The full survey questionnaire is provided in **Appendix 1. Survey Questionnaire**.

Before launching the survey, we conducted a pilot test to gather feedback on question clarity, survey length, and usability. Based on this feedback, adjustments were made to refine the survey structure and address technical issues to ensure a smooth completion process.

A quick registration on the site was required prior to filling out the questionnaire, in order to gather data on the identity of the respondents. The downside of this approach is the potential to discourage participation, resulting in a lower number of completed questionnaires. To mitigate this risk, an ad hoc registration and redirect flow was implemented, as illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 1 Steps for Submitting the Survey on the COcyber Website

The flow operates as follows: when a user accesses the questionnaire URL (e.g., via email or social media), if they are not already registered, they are directed to a courtesy page. Here, they are offered the option to log in or register.

- If the user logs in, they are automatically redirected to the questionnaire page.
- If they register, they receive a confirmation email upon completing the registration. By clicking the confirmation link in the email, they are redirected to the questionnaire page.

This flow is designed to help users maintain focus during the registration process and to minimise the risk of them leaving the site before completing the questionnaire.

In **Step 4** the Dissemination strategy is included. The survey was hosted online on the main page of the COcyber project website to maximise visibility. A dissemination strategy was developed to increase reach and response rates.

AUSTRALO leads the communication and dissemination activities in COyber (under WP5), and this partner provided and implemented an overall strategy for needs assessment survey communication. The active

promotion campaign was launched on January the 7th and running until January 23rd, including a mixed portfolio of marketing tools and channels, notably:

- **A marketing kit** was shared across the COcyber consortium so that all partners share the survey efficiently in their respective networks. This kit included an email message template, a visual banner and templates for social media posts.

Figure 2 Survey Promotion Banner

- **Posting on social media** where the project team posted the survey in its own channels on LinkedIn and on Bluesky but also, got engagement from its followers sharing the survey post on their own channel.
 - AUSTRALO implemented a **LinkedIn Premium Campaign**, running from January 7th, 2025, for seven days, which is a paid advertisement to boost visibility among key audiences. This post resulted in 17 reposts, 208 clicks & 40K impressions.

Figure 3 LinkedIn Paid Advertisement of the Survey

- Also, the information was shared across 10+ **LinkedIn Groups** specialised in cybersecurity topics and gathering experts on the area. This resulted into 430 members being reached (according to the LinkedIn statistics tool).
- **One-to-one messaging campaign** with a tailored email message inviting the COcyber community contacts to submit a response to the survey and/or spread the survey within their

networks. In total, over **600** direct emails were sent for marketing the survey, notably to the COcyber community contacts, partners’ respective networks, Horizon Europe Digital National Contact Points, and European Digital Innovation Hubs dedicated to cybersecurity topics.

- **A dedicated blog article²** was published on the COcyber platform.
- **The project’s first press release (PR#1³)**, shared with European journalists specialised in digital topics, also promoted the running survey.
- **The European sister project’s** (e.g., the ECYBRIDGE, CyberStand, SecureCyber Project Cluster) were contacted to leverage their networks of cybersecurity experts.
- EIT Digital requested the COcyber project officer at the ECCC to promote the survey across their channels.

And finally, follow-up reminders were also sent to encourage participation. The survey included disclaimers about data usage and confidentiality to build trust with respondents and ensure compliance with GDPR regulations.

The last step, **Step 5**, was the survey launched on 03.01.2025 and closed on 24.01.2025. In total, we received 34 responses from various stakeholders. Below is a summary of respondents’ demographics from the survey responses:

Of the 34 respondents, 82% indicate that they are involved in cybersecurity collaboration. Additionally, 58% of respondents have over 10 years of experience in the field. Below, we present the distribution of respondents across countries and sectors, providing insights into the diversity of the group.

Figure 4 and Figure 5. Demographic information, Country and Sector.

Figure 4 Respondents' Country/Region

² <https://cocyber.eu/article-news/online-survey-needs-coordination-between-cybersecurity-civilian-and-defence-spheres>

³ <https://zenodo.org/records/14608663>

Figure 5 Respondents' Sector

A detailed analysis of the Survey can be found in **Appendix 6. Detailed analysis of the survey**. Additionally, the **Appendix 10. BUSINESS INTELLIGENCE TOOL** includes a Business Intelligence Tool based on Power BI, which **allows for dynamic data exploration from different perspectives and can be integrated into the COcyber Platform**.

The survey proved to be less productive than the other two streams (focus groups and VIP interviews), which was anticipated given that our primary focus was on the more in-depth approaches. The survey's scope was intentionally more limited, with questions designed to gather broad, high-level insights rather than detailed qualitative data. In contrast, the interviews and focus groups allowed for a deeper exploration of key topics. As a result, the survey responses primarily served to validate and reinforce the knowledge already acquired through the focus groups and interviews, rather than providing entirely new insights.

Quality control and preliminary results verification with team members

As part of the quality control process, the team conducted a thorough verification of preliminary results. This involved cross-referencing and validating the data/information gathered from the three distinct streams to ensure consistency and reliability. The streams included focus groups, VIP interviews, and survey responses, each contributing complementary insights.

During this cross-checking process, the team identified no significant contradictions or discrepancies across the information gathered. This alignment among the three streams reinforces the validity of the findings and demonstrates a strong degree of coherence across the data sources. The consistent results serve as a solid foundation for the subsequent analysis and interpretation phases of the report.

Incorporating project outcomes into COcyber's work packages

The results obtained from the three research streams are expected to play a significant role in shaping and guiding the upcoming tasks of the COcyber project. Specifically, insights derived from the needs assessment analysis will help in informing the development of the roadmap & coordination activities (T2.3). The survey analysis has the potential to inform recommendations aimed at enhancing the Cybersecurity Observatory and refining the platform developed under WP3. Several survey questions were intentionally designed to address these aspects, ensuring targeted feedback for improvement.

During the VIP interviews and focus groups, participants were invited to provide suggestions related to best practices across the EU and to identify potential national case studies that could be leveraged for WP4. These discussions aimed to gather valuable input that aligns with the project's goals and ensures a practical and actionable approach. Additionally, the needs assessment analysis is expected to contribute broadly to the thematic focus areas of the planned information-sharing activities throughout the project's

duration, particularly under WP4, and to scope the challenges that will be addressed through the Cocyber Hackathon (D5.2).

2 Rationale for strengthened collaboration

2.1 Literature review summary: identifying current frameworks and gaps

Many cybersecurity and data protection frameworks are designed with specific goals and use cases in mind, often tailored to the needs of particular sectors. As a result, they may leave gaps when addressing broader or interconnected challenges, such as those involving cross-sector collaboration. In Appendix 8. LR frameworks & case studies, a SWOT analysis of 54 frameworks and 67 case studies was made to have the possibility to identify gaps and challenges.

While existing cybersecurity frameworks provide critical guidelines and tools for managing risks and ensuring compliance, several gaps persist that hinder their effectiveness in addressing comprehensive cybersecurity needs:

- **Fragmentation.** The lack of integration between frameworks often leads to siloed implementations, making it difficult for organisations to create unified cybersecurity strategies.
- **Limited Cross-Sector Collaboration.** Frameworks focus heavily on defence, while others are tailored for critical infrastructure. This creates gaps in addressing interdependencies between civilian and defence sectors.
- **Evolving Threat Landscape.** Many frameworks struggle to keep pace with rapidly emerging threats, such as sophisticated ransomware attacks or advanced persistent threats (APTs), leaving gaps in guidance for addressing vulnerabilities.
- **Limited Focus on Innovation and Emerging Technologies.** Few frameworks address the cybersecurity implications of emerging technologies like AI, quantum computing, or IoT, leaving gaps in future-proofing security strategies.

By identifying and addressing these gaps, organisations can enhance the effectiveness of existing frameworks, fostering more comprehensive and collaborative cybersecurity practices across sectors and regions.

Together with the Cocyber project, another initiative that try to minimise the gap between civilian and defence sectors is the **ECYBRIDGE**⁴ project. Both initiatives are dedicated to enhancing cybersecurity across Europe by fostering collaboration between civilian and defence sectors. Recognising the intertwined nature of these domains in today's digital landscape, the ECYBRIDGE project aims to create a cohesive strategy that bolsters Europe's resilience against emerging cyber threats. The project seeks to

⁴ The EU Cybersecurity Technology Roadmap. Strengthening Synergies in Defence and Civilian Cybersecurity | ECYBRIDGE project <https://ecybridge.eu/>

bridge gaps in communication, resource allocation, and strategic planning. This unified approach not only strengthens the collective cybersecurity posture but also ensures comprehensive and well-coordinated responses to cyber threats across sectors.

Observatories and Interactive Maps. To identify observatories or platforms that bridge civilian and defence sectors in cybersecurity, here are a few well-regarded ones based on their roles in information-sharing, collaboration, and resources for both sectors:

Name	Description	Observatory includes
European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA)⁵	ENISA provides a range of resources, including threat reports, training materials, and guidelines for both public and private sectors.	Reports, corporate documents, notes, opinion papers, indexes, speeches (by type and year); education platform, maturity self-assessment tool, National Cybersecurity Assessment Framework (NCAF) Tool, list of good practices, toolkit for establishing and developing Information Sharing and Analysis Centres (ISAC), On-line tool for the security of personal data processing, Computer Security Incident Response Teams (CSIRTs) by Country – Interactive Map, National Cyber Security Strategies – Interactive Map, National Cybersecurity Strategies Evaluation Tool, CYBERHEAD – Cybersecurity Higher Education Database.
Cybersecurity Atlas (by the European Commission)⁶	A digital map connecting research organisations and initiatives focused on cybersecurity, facilitating collaboration across civilian and defence sectors	Competence Community (an interactive map showing the location and expertise of cybersecurity organisations and their areas of expertise); Cybersecurity taxonomy (Defining cybersecurity terminologies to ensure harmonisation); Women4Cyber (promote, encourage and support the participation of women in the field of cybersecurity) ; Four pilot projects (Concordia, Echo, Sparta, Cyber security for EU) for the European Cybersecurity Competence Network.
NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence (CCDCOE)⁷	This forum brings together expertise from government, private sector, and academia to advance cyber capacity building.	Hub brings together knowledge on international cyber capacity building tools, publications, indexes, activities on cyber capacity building globally, events, Working Group outcomes. Interactive map of 1025 actors, 9 events and 969 projects in different countries (sorted by region).

⁵ European Union Agency for Cybersecurity. (n.d.). ENISA. Retrieved November 10, 2024, from <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/>

⁶ European Commission. (n.d.). Cybersecurity Atlas. Retrieved November 10, 2024, from <https://cybersecurity-atlas.ec.europa.eu/>

⁷ NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence. (n.d.). CCDCOE. Retrieved November 10, 2024, from <https://ccdcoe.org/>

<p>Global Forum on Cyber Expertise (GFCE)⁸</p>	<p>This forum brings together expertise from government, private sector, and academia to advance cyber capacity building.</p>	<p>Hub brings together knowledge on international cyber capacity building tools, publications, indexes, activities on cyber capacity building globally, events, Working Group outcomes. Interactive map of 1025 actors, 9 events and 969 projects in different countries (sorted by region).</p>
<p>EU Cybersecurity Observatory (by the European Commission)⁹</p>	<p>Part of the EU's digital initiative, this observatory aims to connect sectors by providing an overview of cybersecurity trends, threat landscapes, and best practices.</p>	<p>Policies (Digital Society, Advanced Digital Technologies, International Cooperation in Digital, Digital Economy); Library (Factsheet / infographic, Policy and legislation, Report / Study, Speech, Video, Brochure, Event report, Success story, Call document, Consultation results); Funding (Call for tenders, Call for proposals); Consultations; AI office (centre of AI expertise across the EU. It plays a key role in implementing the AI Act – especially for general-purpose AI – fostering the development and use of trustworthy AI, and international cooperation).</p>
<p>World Economic Forum. Centre for Cybersecurity¹⁰</p>	<p>Global initiative that aims to enhance cyber resilience and shape a secure digital future. Launched to foster collaboration across the public and private sectors.</p>	<p>Publication, research and interactive maps that made with the aim to support 9 initiatives: Cyber Resilience in Oil & Gas, Cyber Resilience in Manufacturing, Cyber Resilience in the Electricity Industry, Partnership against Cybercrime (Cybercrime Atlas), Bridging the Cyber Skills Gap, Cybersecurity Learning Hub, AI & Cyber Initiative, Quantum Security, Global Cybersecurity Outlook 2024.</p>

Table 4 Observatories and Interactive Maps

Identifying current frameworks and gaps in cybersecurity reveals key challenges and trends. Notably, 52%¹¹ of public organisations cite resource and skill shortages as primary obstacles in designing for cyber resilience, while 71%¹² report unfilled cybersecurity roles. Further, 95%¹³ of cyber leaders emphasise the need for enhanced recruitment efforts. Over the last decade, there has been a clear trend toward integrating more robust cybersecurity components into existing programs, addressing both immediate and long-term needs for skilled professionals and resilient frameworks.

⁸ Global Forum on Cyber Expertise. (n.d.). GFCE. Retrieved November 10, 2024, from <https://thegfce.org/>
⁹ European Commission. (n.d.). EU Cybersecurity Observatory. Retrieved November 10, 2024, from <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/cybersecurity>
¹⁰ World Economic Forum. (n.d.). Centre for Cybersecurity. Retrieved November 10, 2024, from <https://centres.weforum.org/centre-for-cybersecurity/home>
¹¹ World Economic Forum. (2024). Global Cybersecurity Outlook 2024.
¹² ISACA. (2023). State of Cybersecurity 2023.
¹³ Trellix. (n.d.). A Closer Look at the Cyber Talent Gap.

SWOT Analysis. Based on **Literature Review Tool Insights (Appendix 9. Literature Review Tool)**, which includes **338 academic papers, reports and books**, which include **100 works in the Cybersecurity and defence field**, **147 works in Civilian cybersecurity** and **91 works in Dual-use cybersecurity**, we analysed insights. Here’s an analysis of current cybersecurity frameworks following a SWOT approach.

Strengths and weaknesses:

Strengths	Weaknesses
<p>Current cybersecurity frameworks demonstrate robust support in fostering collaboration across civilian and defence sectors, supported by agencies like ENISA and NATO’s CCDCOE. Efforts like the European Cybersecurity Competence Network and observatories (e.g., the Cybersecurity Atlas) create structured knowledge-sharing and data resources that strengthen cross-border resilience. Interactive tools, comprehensive databases, and case studies further contribute to effective information sharing and situational awareness.</p>	<p>Challenges remain within existing structures due to resource shortages and skill gaps, with 52% of public organisations reporting limited cybersecurity resources, and 71% having unfilled roles. There is often a disconnect between civilian and defence approaches, such as differences in security protocols, which can complicate cooperation. Organisational diversity across EU nations results in inconsistent cybersecurity practices and governance models, reducing cohesion and integration efficiency.</p>

Opportunities and Threats:

Opportunities	Threats
<p>Increasing integration of cybersecurity elements in existing EU programs provides opportunities to address workforce gaps and enhance resilience. Initiatives like the Cyber Resilience Learning Hub and co-cyber community consultations are steps toward harmonising policy and crisis management approaches. Additionally, emerging frameworks, like PESCO , DIANA encourage collaborative cyber defence projects that can expand capabilities and bridge institutional divides.</p>	<p>External risks include evolving cyber threats, such as complex attacks on critical infrastructure , and regulatory fragmentation , as not all EU and NATO member states align on policy. Political dynamics, like those seen in disagreements between certain NATO and EU countries, further strain unified defence efforts. Rapid technological advances also pressure frameworks to adapt, risking obsolescence if innovation in cybersecurity protocols lags.</p>

Table 5 Cybersecurity Frameworks SWOT Approach

In summary, EU cybersecurity frameworks show significant strengths in fostering cross-sector collaboration and resource-sharing. However, internal challenges, such as skill shortages and inconsistent governance, limit effectiveness. There are promising opportunities for growth through enhanced integration and collaboration initiatives, though evolving cyber threats and regulatory fragmentation pose ongoing risks. Strengthening alignment and adapting to emerging technologies will be key to enhancing resilience across civilian and defence sectors. Existing literature highlights the necessity for more in-depth research to address critical gaps and enhance understanding in this area.

2.2 Core reasons for strengthening collaboration

The digital era has introduced a new domain of threats where both civilian and defence infrastructures face evolving, complex cyberattacks. Critical services, from power grids to communication networks, serve both civilian and military needs. As hostile actors exploit these interdependencies, working in isolation is no longer a viable strategy. By closely aligning cybersecurity efforts, civilian and defence sectors can enhance resilience, agility, and overall security against sophisticated adversaries.

As emerged from the different analysis conducted for this study, the core reasons for strengthening collaboration can be summarised as follows:

- **Growing Complexity of Cyber Threats.** Cyberattacks are increasingly targeting infrastructure and services critical to both civilian life and defence readiness. Traditional boundaries, such as those between public utilities and military supply chains, are blurring. As a result, vulnerabilities in one domain can jeopardise the other.
- **Integrated National Security Posture.** Defence agencies excel in strategic threat intelligence and robust protocols, while civilian sectors bring innovation, agility, and user-focused solutions. Combining these strengths would create a more comprehensive security posture.
- **Shared Targets and Interdependent Systems.** Today's critical infrastructure (such as energy grids, financial networks, healthcare systems, transportation hubs) often serves dual roles. A severe cyberattack on the civilian side can degrade national security, just as a breach in a defence system can spill over into civilian life. Strengthening collaboration ensures that when one side is threatened, both can respond effectively.
- **Resource and Knowledge Optimisation.** Operating in silos often leads to duplicated efforts, fragmented intelligence, and slower responses to emerging threats. By aligning strategies, sharing intelligence, and pooling expertise, civilian and defence sectors can leverage each other's strengths more efficiently.

2.3 Key areas needing closer collaboration

The different qualitative and quantitative methods used in this research highlight that, as cyber threats continue to grow in complexity and scope, the need for closer collaboration between the civilian and defence sectors becomes increasingly critical.

Eight critical areas highlight where civilian-defence cooperation can yield significant benefits:

- **Fragmentation of Cybersecurity Efforts.** Operating in silos leads to overlapping measures, missed opportunities for intelligence sharing, and vulnerabilities at the seams.
- **Limited information sharing.** Without secure and trusted channels for sharing threat intelligence, both sectors respond more slowly and less effectively.
- **Lack of skilled cybersecurity professionals.** Addressing talent shortages requires joint training programs, skill exchanges, and educational partnerships.
- **Scarce dual-use technologies.** Streamlining technology transfer and innovation management ensures both sectors benefit from cutting-edge tools.

- **Uncoordinated Cybersecurity policies.** Harmonising regulatory frameworks reduces inefficiencies and provides clarity for organisations operating in both domains.
- **Need for improved resilience.** Cross-sector collaboration enhances the ability to withstand, adapt to, and recover from cyber incidents.
- **Lack of cutting-edge innovation.** Joint R&D efforts and public-private partnerships can accelerate the development of advanced security solutions.
- **Cultural differences.** Bridging organisational and cultural gaps ensures smoother communication, decision-making, and unified action.

Integrated efforts raise the collective cybersecurity baseline. By addressing fragmentation, improving information sharing, and aligning policies, we minimise attack surfaces and respond more efficiently. In a world of escalating cyber aggression, unified civilian-defence collaboration ensures a stable, secure environment for both public welfare and national security.

2.3.1. Fragmentation of cybersecurity efforts

Cyberattacks are no longer confined to a single domain. Modern attackers exploit the **interconnectedness** of civilian and defence infrastructures, targeting both sectors simultaneously to amplify damage. A successful attack on one sector can cascade to the other, creating vulnerabilities across critical systems.

This fragmentation in cybersecurity efforts makes a **unified approach** essential. Attackers target civilian and defence systems as a whole, yet response **efforts remain fragmented**, with sectors acting independently. By not **pooling strategies, resources, and expertise**, opportunities for a more effective response are missed.

Collaboration enables both sectors to manage crises more effectively and reduces the risk of prolonged disruptions, ensuring a coordinated defence against increasingly sophisticated threats.

To effectively **address the fragmentation** in cybersecurity efforts between the civilian and defence sectors, it's crucial to understand the reasons why collaboration is not just beneficial, but necessary.

These **three key factors underpin the need for a unified approach – as well as amplified issues associated with the fragmentation of efforts:**

- The increasing complexity of cyber threats.
- The shared reliance on critical infrastructure.
- The demand for aligned responses to incidents and crises.

The increasing complexity of cyber threats

The types of cyberattacks we’re seeing now are far more sophisticated, targeting not just one sector at a time. Modern cyberattacks have become significantly more **sophisticated and multifaceted**, often targeting multiple sectors simultaneously. **Attackers do not differentiate between civilian and defence infrastructures**, exploiting their interconnectedness to maximise disruption.

- For instance, a **single cyberattack** might simultaneously hit or impact both civilian infrastructure (like hospitals or power grids) and defence systems (like military networks).
- This is because the line between what’s considered a “civilian target” and what’s considered a “defence target” is getting blurry. **Civilian and defence sectors are interconnected** in ways they weren’t before, so a successful attack on one can impact the other.
- Collaboration is no longer optional. Both sectors face similar threats and must **pool strategies, resources, and expertise to address these new modern threats effectively**.

The issue of fragmentation efforts is therefore amplified by the Shared Threat Landscape across both civilian and defence sectors, as explained in the table below.

Civilian sector’s perspective	Defence sector’s perspective
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By working together with defence entities, these organisations can enhance their preparedness and response capabilities, ensuring that attacks targeting interconnected systems are managed efficiently. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weaknesses in civilian systems directly translate to vulnerabilities in defence operations. • Collaborating with civilian entities ensures that shared risks are addressed, and response times are minimised, bolstering national security during cyber crises.

Table 6 Fragmentation Efforts – Shared Threat Landscape

The shared reliance on critical infrastructure

Modern societies and defence systems are intricately tied to **critical infrastructures**, such as energy grids, telecommunications networks, and transportation systems. These **infrastructures are dual-purpose**, serving both civilian and defence needs.

A **cyberattack targeting one of these infrastructures** can create **simultaneous disruptions** across sectors.

- For example, a cyberattack on a **power grid** might not only result in **widespread civilian blackouts**, but also impact military operations, and **cripple military operations** reliant on that same infrastructure.
- Note that, while the NIS2 directive already mandates robust cybersecurity for critical infrastructure, it alone is not enough. **Real collaboration** between civilian and defence sectors is essential to establish a coordinated defence against such attacks.

The issue of fragmentation efforts has therefore amplified the **Interdependency of Critical Infrastructure** across both the civilian and defence sectors.

Civilian sector’s perspective	Defence sector’s perspective
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> By collaborating with defence organisations, civilian operators can enhance the security of these shared assets, ensuring that they remain functional even during an attack. Such partnerships should also enable proactive threat mitigation and faster recovery when incidents occur. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> By working with civilian entities, defence can ensure that shared vulnerabilities are addressed and that their own operations remain uninterrupted during cyber crises.

Table 7 Fragmentation efforts – Interdependency of Critical Infrastructure

The lack of aligned responses to incidents

In the event of a **large-scale cyberattack**, like ransomware hitting a major energy company, both civilian and defence sectors need to respond quickly to contain the damage.

In the event of a large-scale cyberattacks, such as ransomware hitting and crippling a major energy company, both civilian and defence sectors need to respond quickly to contain the damage. They must respond swiftly and effectively to **mitigate damage**.

However:

- The current response frameworks operate in silos. On one hand, **civilian agencies focus on restoring services and public communication.** And on the other hand, **defence agencies prioritise national security and containment of threats.**
- This **lack of alignment** can lead to delays, miscommunication, and inefficiencies, which **exacerbate the impact** of the attack.

The issue of fragmentation efforts is therefore amplified by the **State-sponsored attacks that are increasingly targeting not only military assets but also critical civilian infrastructures.**

Civilian sector’s perspective	Defence sector’s perspective
<p>Civilian organisations could benefit from:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A faster recovery times when their crisis management protocols are aligned with defence strategies. Minimised disruptions to critical services through shared response efforts. 	<p>Defence operations depend on the resilience of civilian infrastructure, could benefit from:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A coordinated response plan, ensuring that national security efforts are not hindered by weaknesses or delays in civilian recovery processes. A focus on containment while ensuring civilian systems are supported in real time.

Table 8 Fragmentation efforts – State-sponsored attacks

Focus Groups and Interview insights:

- Recent analysis highlights the increasing need for a unified governance structure to manage cross-sector cybersecurity efforts effectively.
- Limited interaction between stakeholders in these sectors exacerbates the gap, leaving key resources underutilised and cyber responses disjointed.

Survey insights:

- The analysis highlights significant differences in how civilian and defence sectors perceive the need for cybersecurity collaboration. While civilians prioritise addressing fragmentation of cybersecurity efforts as key reason, the defence sector places lower emphasis on these issues. Stakeholders classified as "Others" also ranked fragmentation as a top concern, reinforcing the urgency of improving alignment. These disparities highlight the necessity of targeted strategies to bridge collaboration gaps and foster a more cohesive cybersecurity framework.

2.3.2 Lack of (of limited) information-sharing

Cyber threats do not respect **sectoral boundaries**. For instance, a defence agency might uncover a state-sponsored cyberattack targeting both military and civilian infrastructure, while a private company might identify vulnerabilities with implications for defence systems.

Despite facing similar threats, the **civilian and defence sectors often lack robust mechanisms to share crucial intelligence effectively**. Indeed, although civilian and defence sectors often face similar threats, they often have access to different intelligence sources.

This gap in information sharing can lead to missed opportunities for proactive threat mitigation. Emerging threats, such as sophisticated ransomware or zero-day exploits, often require coordinated action across both sectors. While initiatives like those led by ENISA have started to bridge this divide, secure and trusted **channels for intelligence exchange** remain underdeveloped.

By enhancing collaboration and developing structured **frameworks for intelligence sharing**, both sectors can better anticipate and respond to cyber threats, ensuring stronger collective resilience.

Description of the identified issue in the current landscape

The effectiveness of cybersecurity heavily depends on the **speed and accuracy of information sharing**. Yet, intelligence-sharing mechanisms between civilian and defence sectors are often **underdeveloped or restricted by trust barriers**, and insufficient frameworks. These gaps expose both sectors to unnecessary risks from evolving threats, as neither has access to the full picture of potential vulnerabilities or attack vectors.

What are some of the information sharing challenges spotted through our data collection process?

- **Time constraints:** Sharing cybersecurity information often encounters delays due to procedural bottlenecks or misaligned priorities between sectors.
- **Trust barriers:** A lack of secure and trusted channels fosters hesitation, limiting the willingness to share critical intelligence.
- **One-way information sharing:** Intelligence flow tends to be unidirectional (from civil to defence), limiting mutual benefits.

By creating better mechanisms for intelligence sharing—especially when it comes to emerging threats—both sectors can be better prepared. **Sharing intelligence** on vulnerabilities and attack patterns helps prevent large-scale cyber incidents that could impact both critical civilian infrastructure and military systems.

Civilian sector’s perspective	Defence sector’s perspective
<p>Civilian organisations could benefit from information sharing to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Equip civilian organisations with classified, actionable intelligence. Equip civilian organisations with critical intelligence – such as emerging threat profiles or state-sponsored attack indicators – civilian organisations may require to pre-empt or mitigate threats effectively. 	<p>By fostering information-sharing partnerships with civilian organisations, the defence sector could:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gain early insights into emerging threats affecting shared infrastructures. Improve readiness to address vulnerabilities before they are exploited. Ensure national security objectives are not hindered by unaddressed civilian risks.

Table 9 Information-Sharing

Focus Groups and Interview insights:

- The importance of creating secure channels for real-time information sharing is emphasised in recent analyses.
- Current frameworks stress the need for alignment in information-sharing protocols across sectors.

Survey insights:

- Civilians view limited information sharing as a key reason for improving collaboration, whereas the defence sector assigns it less importance. Stakeholders categorised as "Others" consider limited information sharing a moderate concern, further emphasising the need for better alignment. These differing perspectives highlight the importance of developing targeted strategies to address collaboration gaps and create a more unified cybersecurity framework.

2.3.3 Lack of awareness capacity

The **cybersecurity talent gap** is a critical challenge impacting both civilian and defence sectors (European Union Agency for Cybersecurity, 2022). The shortage of skilled professionals limits the capacity to develop resilient systems, detect vulnerabilities, and respond effectively to cyber incidents.

As cyber threats continue to evolve in complexity, the need for a well-trained and adaptable workforce becomes increasingly urgent.

Collaboration between the civilian and defence sectors offers an opportunity to address this challenge. By implementing **joint training programs, shared education initiatives, and standardised cybersecurity certifications**, both sectors can work together to cultivate a workforce capable of tackling future threats. By aligning efforts, civilian and defence organisations can develop a **pipeline of talent** ready to address emerging cybersecurity challenges, ensuring the resilience of critical infrastructures and national security systems.

Description of the identified issue in the current landscape

As cyber threats continue to evolve in complexity, the need for a well-trained and adaptable workforce becomes increasingly urgent. Some key cybersecurity talent capacity challenges identified through our data collection process include:

- A **limited pool of trained professionals** with specialised cybersecurity expertise.
- Teams are struggling to keep **pace with evolving threats**.
- **Inconsistent education and training opportunities** across sectors.
- **Difficulty in attracting talent** due to the specialised nature of roles, especially defence roles.

Developing talent and building & training a skilled workforce is critical for both sectors. Civilian and defence sectors can collaborate by sharing education programs, training opportunities, and cybersecurity certifications to address the talent gap. **By working together, both sectors can cultivate a workforce equipped to address future challenges.**

Civilian sector’s perspective	Defence sector’s perspective
<p>By participating in shared training programs, civilian organisations could enhance their internal capabilities and align their approaches with defence practices.</p> <p>Access to defence expertise could also further strengthen their awareness capacity and preparedness.</p>	<p>The defence sector, tasked with national security, faces a similar talent shortfall.</p> <p>Additionally, defence operations often rely on civilian infrastructure, making the development of a shared cybersecurity workforce critical.</p>

Table 10 Developing Talent and Building & Training a Skilled Workforce

Focus Groups and Interview insights:

- The importance of fostering a collaborative environment for skill development is emphasised in the recommendations of the COcyber project.
- Joint training initiatives can significantly enhance capacity, enabling professionals to understand the needs and operational frameworks of both sectors.

Survey insights:

- The analysis shows differing perspectives on the lack of awareness capacity as a reason for enhancing cybersecurity collaboration. The defence sector evaluates it as the least significant reason, while civilians and stakeholders classified as "Others" regard it as a moderate concern. This contrast highlights the need to address varying levels of prioritisation and to ensure that awareness-building efforts are tailored to the specific needs of each sector.

2.3.4 Lack of dual-use technologies

First, the civilian and defence sectors often use the same cybersecurity technologies (e.g., cybersecurity tools, such as encryption, threat detection, and secure communications systems, are used by both civilian and defence actors).

Second, on top of this common use of technology, many cybersecurity technologies have a dual-use potential, serving both civilian and defence applications or purposes (e.g., cybersecurity technologies such as advanced cryptography or secure cloud infrastructure). Sharing these dual-use technologies and innovations could make both sectors more efficient and avoid duplicated efforts. Nevertheless, the development, innovation, and transfer of these technologies often occur in silos, leading to duplicated efforts, inefficiencies, and missed opportunities for synergy. This lack of collaboration hinders the ability to leverage the potential of shared technologies for mutual benefit fully.

Description of the identified issue in the current landscape

Civilian and defence sectors share similar cybersecurity tools like encryption, intrusion detection systems, and firewalls, with overlapping needs despite differing goals of privacy and national security. Instead of independently developing parallel solutions, collaboration between these sectors can drive innovation, reduce redundancy, and expedite the adoption of dual-use technologies. Below, we list “shared technology” challenges spotted through the data collection:

- Technology Innovation **often happens in silos**. Indeed, Innovation is often contained within either the civilian or defence sector, with few opportunities for shared development.
- Technology transfers are insufficient. There is **a lack of streamlined mechanisms for transferring technologies across sectors** – resulting in higher costs and slower adoption.
- There is a fragmentation of effort in the **parallel development of similar technologies**.

A joint approach to **technology transfer and innovation management** is essential to drive progress and ensure that both civilian and defence sectors benefit from cutting-edge cybersecurity solutions.

Civilian sector’s perspective	Defence sector’s perspective
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<p>The civilian sector stands to gain significantly from defence-driven innovations, which often prioritise higher levels of security. These advanced technologies can provide:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to cutting-edge cybersecurity tools that would otherwise be out of reach due to resource constraints. By collaborating, civilian entities can benefit from adopting defensive techniques, such as real-time intrusion detection systems and threat intelligence platforms. • Enhanced protection for sensitive information and critical infrastructures. <p>Collaborating with the defence sector could ensure that civilians benefit from proven solutions, avoiding the need to develop equally robust technologies independently.</p>	<p>The defence sector can leverage civilian-developed technologies to address its cybersecurity challenges more quickly. Civilian solutions, particularly dual-use technologies, offer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broader application of scalable technologies, such as those in the digital product space governed by the Cyber Resilience Act. • Faster adoption of proven innovations without needing to start from scratch. • Cost savings by avoiding the duplication of development efforts. <p>By adopting civilian technologies, the defence sector can focus its resources on mission-specific innovations while benefiting from civilian expertise and market-driven solutions.</p>
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Table 11 Technology Transfer and Innovation Management

Focus Groups and Interview insights:

- Dual-use technologies play a critical role in improving cybersecurity capabilities across sectors.
- Existing frameworks, such as the European Defence Agency’s research on dual-use technologies, provide valuable lessons for managing innovation and technology transfer

Survey insights:

- The analysis reveals a shared perspective among all respondent groups regarding the lack of dual-use technologies as a reason for enhancing cybersecurity collaboration. Civilians, defence stakeholders, and others consistently evaluate it as a moderate concern, indicating a mutual recognition of its importance in fostering collaboration and addressing cybersecurity challenges across sectors.

2.3.5 Lack of coordinated cybersecurity policies

The civilian and defence sectors often operate under **disparate cybersecurity policies** driven by **differing priorities**. Civilian policies typically emphasise **privacy, compliance**, and the protection of individual rights, while defence policies focus on **national security** and operational readiness. These differing priorities can lead to bureaucratic delays and ineffective responses. These contrasting approaches can, therefore, create loopholes that cyber attackers can exploit. These can lead to **gaps** and **inconsistencies** that cyber attackers may exploit. A **coordinated policy framework** would allow civilian and defence entities to address cybersecurity risks comprehensively and proactively, reducing the

likelihood of exploitation by adversaries. By collaborating, both sectors can work towards harmonised policies that balance privacy with security.

Description of the identified issue in the current landscape

Currently, there is a significant **lack of alignment** between the policies governing cybersecurity in the civilian and defence sectors.

- Civilian cybersecurity policies primarily focus on **protecting individual privacy** and adhering to regulations such as GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation).
- In contrast, defence policies are driven by the imperative to safeguard **national security** and ensure operational readiness.

This mismatch in priorities and regulatory frameworks creates **gaps** that cybercriminals can exploit. For example, privacy regulations might delay the defence sector’s response to incidents affecting civilian systems, leaving both sectors vulnerable to further exploitation.

What are some of the “Lack of coordinated cybersecurity policies” challenges spotted through our data collection process?

- **Bureaucratic delays** are caused by conflicting requirements and unaligned objectives. There are **delays in response efforts** due to conflicts between privacy rules and defence priorities.
- **Inefficiencies in responding to incidents** that require cooperation across sectors. Regulatory requirements are creating a barrier to present a unified front against cyber threats.

Civilian sector’s perspective	Defence sector’s perspective
Collaborating with defence agencies to harmonise cybersecurity policies would: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simplify compliance by reducing conflicts between privacy and security requirements. • Strengthen overall resilience against cyber threats targeting shared infrastructures. 	Collaborating with civilian sector to harmonise cybersecurity policies would: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure access to civilian systems during incidents – that is no longer limited or restricted due to privacy restrictions. • Ensure a faster response, by pro-actively eliminating bureaucratic barriers and uncoordinated procedures.

Table 12 Harmonising Cybersecurity Policies

Focus Groups and Interview insights:

- Harmonising cybersecurity policies is critical to reducing inefficiencies and ensuring cohesive responses to cyber threats. The NIS2 directive serves as a valuable model for aligning civilian and defence priorities.
- Recent studies emphasise the need for centralised governance structures to oversee policy alignment and streamline regulatory processes.

Survey insights:

- The analysis indicates that all respondent groups (civilians, defence stakeholders, and others) consistently view the lack of coordinated cybersecurity policies as a moderate concern. This shared perspective highlights the recognition of policy fragmentation as a challenge, while also suggesting that it is not perceived as an urgent priority compared to other factors influencing cybersecurity collaboration.

2.3.6 Lack of cross-pollination of ideas and best practices

Cybersecurity resilience – the ability to prevent, respond to, and recover from cyberattacks – can be significantly enhanced through **cross-pollination of ideas and practices** between the civilian and defence sectors. Each sector brings unique strengths to the table:

- **Civilian approaches** often focus on **risk management**, emphasising flexibility, compliance, and the minimisation of operational disruptions.
- **Defence protocols** prioritise **rigorous security measures**, including strict access controls, layered defences, and continuous monitoring.

By adopting and integrating each other's **best practices**, both sectors can bolster their **resilience** against cyber threats. For example:

- Civilians can incorporate **defence-grade protocols** to strengthen their cybersecurity posture.
- The defence sector can leverage **risk management methodologies** to anticipate and mitigate risks more effectively.

This collaboration creates a **synergistic effect**, enabling both sectors to build **stronger defences**, respond more efficiently to attacks, and recover more quickly from disruptions.

Description of the identified issue in the current landscape

When civilian and defence sectors **collaborate**, both benefit from a **cross-pollination of ideas and practices**, leading to improved resilience against cyberattacks. As presented, each sector brings unique strengths. By adopting **each other's best practices**, both sectors can strengthen their ability to prevent, respond to, and recover from cyber threats.

Civilian sector’s perspective	Defence sector’s perspective
<p>The civilian sector can enhance its cybersecurity strategies by integrating defence-level security practices into its operations. Civilians can incorporate defence-grade protocols to strengthen their cybersecurity posture.</p> <p>This collaboration would enable civilians to fortify their defences while maintaining the flexibility required in open, interconnected environments.</p>	<p>The defence sector can leverage the civilian sector’s expertise in risk management and rapid recovery after attacks.</p> <p>This collaboration would enable the defence sector to anticipate and mitigate risks more effectively..</p>

Table 13 Adopting Best Practices

Focus Groups and Interview insights:

- Stakeholders highlights the importance of integrated crisis management frameworks to ensure rapid and effective responses to cyberattacks.
- The need for cross-sector coordination to address the increasing sophistication of cyber threats.

Survey insights:

- The analysis shows that need for improved resilience is consistently viewed as medium concerns across all respondent groups. This indicates a shared recognition of the importance of fostering collaboration to exchange knowledge and strengthen resilience, even though these factors are not seen as the most pressing priorities.

2.3.7 Lack of cutting-edge innovation

Promoting research & innovation is vital for staying ahead of new threats. One might even argue that Innovation is the cornerstone of staying ahead in the cybersecurity landscape. It is critical for maintaining a proactive stance in the ever-evolving cybersecurity landscape. However, the lack of coordination between civilian and defence sectors results in **fragmented research efforts** and **isolated advancements**. This, in turn, **slows the pace of progress** and leaves both sectors vulnerable to emerging threats.

Collaboration between civilian and defence sectors can accelerate innovation by **sharing innovation**, **sharing research**, and **co-developing technologies**. Joint initiatives can ensure both sectors remain ahead of emerging threats, creating a safer and more secure digital future. This is particularly relevant for emerging technologies like quantum computing, AI, and machine learning, which have applications in both fields.

As previously mentioned, both sectors use similar cybersecurity technologies, and the opportunity for collaboration in developing such technologies is significant. Both could benefit from a collaboration

approach as they have complementary approaches: civilian entities often lead in innovation and rapid technological development, while defence sectors bring security expertise and robust security protocols.

Description of the identified issue in the current landscape

Civilian and defence sectors often work independently, leading to duplicated efforts, **slower development, and a lack of shared breakthroughs**. By sharing research findings, and co-developing technologies, both sectors can accelerate innovation. We list below the “Lack of Innovation” challenges spotted through the data collection:

- **Limited access to state-of-the-art** technologies that could enhance resilience.
- **Higher costs due to duplicating R&D** efforts already undertaken by the other sector.
- **Slower adoption of breakthrough solutions**, leaving them more vulnerable to advanced threats.

Promoting joint **R&D** initiatives is crucial for both sectors to remain resilient and adaptable in an increasingly complex digital landscape.

Civilian sector’s perspective	Defence sector’s perspective
<p>Collaboration with the defence sector would allow civilians to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leverage advanced tools and techniques developed in defence labs. • Share resources to lower costs and accelerate innovation cycles. 	<p>Collaboration with civilian organisations would allow the defence sector to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adopt flexible solutions from civilian R&D that can enhance defence capabilities. • Benefit from the agility of market-driven innovations to address rapidly evolving threats. • Build dual-use technologies that cater to the needs of both sectors while saving time and resources.

Table 14 Joint Initiatives

Focus Groups and Interview insights:

- Stakeholders emphasises the importance of fostering environments where innovation can thrive across both sectors.
- Existing frameworks, such as the European Defence Agency’s efforts in dual-use technology research, provide valuable examples of how innovation can be promoted collaboratively

Survey insights:

- The analysis reveals contrasting views on the lack of cutting-edge innovation as a reason for enhancing cybersecurity collaboration. The defence sector prioritises this issue, considering it a significant factor, while civilians and stakeholders classified as “Others” rank it as the least important concern. This divergence highlights differing priorities between sectors, with defence focusing on technological advancement and innovation, while civilians and others place greater emphasis on other challenges.

2.3.8 Cultural differences between the two sectors

The cultural divide between civilian and defence sectors represents a significant barrier to achieving seamless collaboration in cybersecurity. Each sector operates within its own set of deeply entrenched norms and practices that often diverge significantly. This divergence is particularly evident in organisational structures, communication dynamics, and decision-making approaches.

While both sectors aim to address the growing complexity of cyber threats, their differing operational paradigms and priorities can lead to friction, miscommunication, and inefficiencies. Understanding and addressing these cultural differences is essential for fostering a cohesive cybersecurity ecosystem that leverages the strengths of both sectors.

Description of the identified issue in the current landscape

Cultural differences between the civilian and defence sectors present significant challenges to effective collaboration in cybersecurity. These differences are deeply rooted in variations in **organisational structures, communication styles, decision-making processes, and overall workflows**.

Bridging these divides is critical to fostering partnerships that are not only operationally efficient but also capable of achieving shared cybersecurity objectives.

- Defence organisations traditionally operate within “rigid” hierarchical frameworks that emphasise **strict protocols, discipline, and chain-of-command decision-making**, with well-defined roles and responsibilities.
- In contrast, civilian organisations often adopt **more flexible, decentralised, and consensus-driven approaches**. They emphasise collaboration and innovation, often allowing greater flexibility and autonomy at individual and team levels.

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While these differences reflect the distinct missions and priorities of each sector, they can hinder mutual understanding, trust, and the timely exchange of information.

Additional obstacles arise from differences in priorities, and organisational cultures, which can further complicate efforts to establish common ground.

- The defence sector may **prioritise national security** above all else.
- In contrast, civilian entities are more focused on **data privacy, compliance, and service continuity**, which are more in line with service delivery, and customer satisfaction.

On top of this, **additional obstacles may also further arise from differences in terminology and communication style**.

These disparities can result in misaligned goals, slowed decision-making, and an overall lack of cohesion in joint operations.

- Variations in **terminology** and technical jargon can create barriers to collaboration.

By fostering mutual understanding, building trust, and developing shared frameworks for communication and decision-making, stakeholders can overcome barriers and establish stronger partnerships. Through initiatives such as **joint training programs, cultural exchanges, and standardised protocols**, both sectors can move toward a more cohesive and resilient cybersecurity ecosystem. Addressing cultural differences is not merely a matter of convenience but a strategic imperative for safeguarding national security and public welfare in an increasingly complex digital landscape.

Civilian sector’s perspective	Defence sector’s perspective
<p>Civilian organisations could benefit from:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The defence sector’s highly structured decision-making processes, especially during critical incidents requiring swift action. • Exposure to defence-grade protocols to strengthen civilian cybersecurity postures, particularly in areas like access control and layered defences. 	<p>Defence sector could benefit from:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leveraging the civilian sector’s agility and innovative approaches, particularly in adapting to rapidly changing technological landscapes. • Learning from the decentralised workflows of civilian organisations may help the defence sector streamline non-critical operations and reduce procedural bottlenecks.

Table 15 Cultural Differences

Focus Groups and Interview insights:

- Stakeholders highlights the need for joint exercises and workshops to foster mutual understanding and trust between civilian and defence stakeholders.
- Establishing cultural exchange programmes and promoting cross-sector dialogue are identified as effective strategies for bridging these divides.
- Participants emphasised the importance of creating shared frameworks for communication and decision-making to ensure alignment during cybersecurity incidents.

Survey insights:

- The analysis highlights differing perspectives on cultural differences as a reason for enhancing cybersecurity collaboration. The defence sector prioritises this issue, viewing it as a significant factor, while civilians and stakeholders classified as "Others" rank it among the least important concerns. This contrast reflects the defence sector's focus on overcoming organisational and operational barriers, whereas civilians and others place less emphasis on cultural alignment in their collaboration priorities.

A detailed analysis of the Survey can be found in **Appendix 6. Detailed analysis of the survey.**

2.4 Potential solutions for enhanced collaboration

Below is a set of recommendations extrapolated from literature review, focus groups, interview and survey illustrating solutions for enhanced collaboration in the critical areas identified in the previous chapter, and how each proposed initiative could function in practice. Each entry outlines its purpose, the mechanisms by which it would operate, and the benefits it would bring to strengthening collaboration between civilian and defence cybersecurity spheres.

ID	Solution	Description	For the civilian sector:	For the defence sector:
A.1	Civil Society, academia, Broad COcyber Community	These teams combine civilian IT experts, defence cyber units, and possibly private-sector specialists into rapid-reaction groups. Activated immediately during an incident, they coordinate actions—such as isolating compromised systems and remediating vulnerabilities—to ensure swift, unified responses. By sharing expertise and resources, they minimise downtime and prevent attackers from exploiting siloed defences.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborate with defence sectors to improve cybersecurity efforts. Access advanced defence technologies for better protection. Engage in joint simulations to enhance operational readiness. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gain insights from civilian expertise in technology development. Share military-grade security protocols with civilian partners. Foster innovation through joint research and development efforts.
A.2	Dual-Use Technology Agreements	Formalised agreements clarify how innovations benefiting both civilian and defence arenas can be shared and adapted. Such contracts detail ownership rights, licensing terms, and security requirements, making it easier for cutting-edge encryption tools, threat detection systems, or secure communications platforms to flow seamlessly between sectors.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Faster access to high-grade solutions. Clear legal frameworks for IP protection. Enhanced cybersecurity across industries. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Broader R&D collaboration. Streamlined technology transfer. Maintained security protocols to protect sensitive tech.
A.3	Real-Time Threat Intelligence Sharing Platforms	Secure digital hubs allow approved users to share cyber threat data—malicious IP addresses, evolving malware signatures, newly discovered vulnerabilities—in near real-time. Access controls, encryption, and standardised data formats ensure that both civilian agencies and defence bodies can quickly incorporate fresh intelligence into their protective measures.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to classified threat intelligence strengthens civilian defences. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Civilian entities face similar threats. Their experiences help anticipate broader threats.
A.4	Joint Cybersecurity Training Programs	Integrated training curricula bring together civilian IT staff, military cyber teams, and even industry professionals. Using simulations and scenario-based exercises, participants learn to understand each other's protocols, legal constraints, and tools. This approach builds a common skill set and fosters interpersonal trust and familiarity, strengthening overall readiness.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Civilian cybersecurity teams experience high-stakes simulations. They gain insights from military-grade security practices. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The defence sector learns how civilian systems operate. Understanding specific challenges builds collaboration and trust in real-world scenarios.

A.5	Integrated Crisis Management Frameworks	Unified plans detail escalation procedures, command chains, and communication protocols for handling large-scale cyber incidents. Civilian emergency managers, defence strategists, and policymakers jointly develop these frameworks, ensuring that when attacks strike, all parties know their roles, can coordinate messages, and avoid duplication of effort or conflicting directives.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear communication protocols. • Minimised overlaps in responsibilities. • Rapid coordination across multiple agencies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Streamlined command and control. • Unified policy-driven responses. • Reduced risk of conflicting directives.
A.6	Shared Resource Allocation	Instead of each sector purchasing and deploying its own tools independently, frameworks for shared resource allocation allow critical assets—such as forensic equipment, secure data centres, or specialised cybersecurity software—to be pooled. This not only lowers costs but also ensures that both sectors can quickly access advanced capabilities when needed.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower operational costs. • Immediate access to high-end tools. • Coordinated investment and maintenance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimised use of specialised resources. • Enhanced operational readiness. • Reduced redundancy and faster deployment.
A.7	Harmonised Cybersecurity Framework	A standardised set of guidelines, technical standards, and best practices helps civilian, and defence bodies implement compatible security measures. By agreeing on baseline criteria—e.g., encryption strength, logging policies, incident reporting formats—they reduce confusion and ensure consistent protection levels across all critical infrastructure.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardised technologies reduce costs and complexity in managing cybersecurity. • This improves overall resilience across different systems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardisation ensures military operations can rely on civilian infrastructures, like energy and telecommunications, during crises. • This improves operational readiness without compatibility issues.
A.8	Cybersecurity Governance Framework	Clear governance structures outline responsibilities, authorities, and decision-making processes. Under such a framework, government agencies, military cyber commands, and private partners know who leads in a crisis, how budgets are allocated, how to handle data classification, and how to address legal and regulatory hurdles.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A clear governance body gives civilian agencies and industries a voice in decision-making, ensuring their needs are addressed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhances communication and collaboration with civilian entities, integrating defence priorities into broader cybersecurity strategies for cohesive national and regional policies.

A.9	Public-Private Cybersecurity Partnerships	By involving private industry, these partnerships tap into cutting-edge tech solutions, up-to-date threat intelligence, and specialised skills. Civilian and defence stakeholders jointly collaborate with vendors, research labs, and service providers, enabling continuous innovation and rapid integration of new defensive measures into both public and defence networks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to specialised tech and expertise. • Up-to-date threat intelligence sharing. • Faster adoption of innovative cyber defences. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broader industry collaboration. • Accelerated technology integration. • Enhanced synergy with private R&D initiatives.
A.10	National Cybersecurity Simulations	Regular, large-scale exercises simulate complex, multi-vector cyberattacks on critical infrastructures. Participants from civilian and defence organisations test response plans, identify gaps, and refine protocols. Post-exercise reviews lead to lessons learned and improved resilience, ensuring that future real-world incidents are managed more effectively.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Realistic stress-testing of systems. • Improved coordination with defence entities. • Refined crisis communication strategies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comprehensive readiness validation. • Identification of strategic vulnerabilities. • Better alignment with civilian emergency procedures.
A.11	Cross-Sector Crisis Management	Establish formalised vulnerability disclosure mechanisms that enable secure, timely reporting of cyber weaknesses affecting critical infrastructure. Civilian and defence entities would share standardised procedures for receiving, verifying, and addressing vulnerabilities. By quickly collaborating to fix issues, both sectors can pre-empt attacks, minimise damage, and enhance trust in their joint security efforts.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civilian companies and agencies can recover more quickly from cyberattacks when their crisis management protocols are aligned with defence sectors, preventing disjointed responses. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defence operations are less likely to be disrupted if civilian infrastructure (such as energy, transportation, and communication) is part of a coordinated response plan, making national recovery more efficient.
A.12	Create Cybersecurity Innovation Hubs	Innovation hubs serve as collaborative ecosystems where academics, industry researchers, civilian agencies, and defence entities co-develop new solutions. By offering shared labs, funding opportunities, and intellectual property frameworks, these hubs accelerate the production and testing of advanced security tools relevant to both sectors.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accelerated innovation improves security. • Dual-use technologies enhance critical infrastructure resilience. • Economic growth supports startups and job creation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stronger cyber defences from collaborative solutions. • Adoption of robust technologies for military applications. • Enhanced resilience in defence infrastructures.

A.13	Launch Joint Cybersecurity R&D Initiatives	Multi-year research programs tackle emerging cybersecurity challenges—like quantum-resistant cryptography or AI-driven threat detection. Civilian and defence organisations share costs, expertise, and testing facilities, creating a pipeline of advanced technologies that strengthens national cyber capabilities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Innovations from defence can improve security in banking, healthcare, and other industries. Dual-use technologies increase adaptability and reduce costs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Defence gains access to cutting-edge civilian innovations, boosting national security through collaboration. Dual-use technologies are critical for military communications and infrastructure.
A.14	Cross-Sector Cybersecurity Workshops	Regular workshops encourage open dialogue, knowledge exchange, and best practice sharing. Civilian sysadmins and defence cyber officers learn from each other's experiences. These events identify common challenges—such as shortage of talent or complex regulations—and work toward shared solutions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Platforms for knowledge sharing and best practices. Opportunities to coordinate responses to threats with defence counterparts. Joint development of solutions for critical infrastructure protection. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved collaboration with civilian agencies on cybersecurity priorities. Enhanced incident response through shared protocols and exercises. Opportunities to learn from private sector innovations and best practices.
A.15	Cross-Sector Cybersecurity Workshops	Regular workshops encourage open dialogue, knowledge exchange, and best practice sharing. Civilian sysadmins and defence cyber officers learn from each other's experiences. These events identify common challenges—such as shortage of talent or complex regulations—and work toward shared solutions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Platforms for knowledge sharing and best practices. Opportunities to coordinate responses to threats with defence counterparts. Joint development of solutions for critical infrastructure protection. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved collaboration with civilian agencies on cybersecurity priorities. Enhanced incident response through shared protocols and exercises. Opportunities to learn from private sector innovations and best practices.
A.16	Cybersecurity Awareness Campaigns	Public-facing initiatives build general cybersecurity literacy. By teaching citizens and employees in both sectors about phishing, strong password practices, and the importance of updates, these campaigns reduce human-error vulnerabilities and ensure everyone, from frontline staff to top executives, is alert and informed.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Focus on education for employees and the general public. Utilise tailored messaging highlighting specific cybersecurity threats. Engage the public through social media campaigns and workshops. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prioritise training for defence personnel on advanced cybersecurity practices. Collaborate with national cybersecurity centres. Address specific defence sector concerns and threats through tailored workshops.
A.17	Exchange Programs	Temporary staff rotations enable civilian analysts to gain insight into defence cyber operations and vice versa. Immersion in another sector's environment broadens perspectives, improves empathy, and increases the fluidity of cross-sector collaboration when crises arise.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gains defence expertise in security protocols and threat intelligence, improving critical infrastructure protection. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learn from civilian expertise in emerging technologies, enhancing defence cybersecurity capabilities.

A.18	Collaborative Threat Intelligence Networks	<p>These networks extend beyond real-time platforms by setting up longer-term alliances among analysts who routinely share datasets, research findings, and toolkits. Over time, this fosters a community of practitioners who trust each other, maintain ongoing dialogues, and rapidly disseminate critical updates.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous flow of actionable intel. • Strengthened community ties. • Faster detection and response to emerging threats. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced situational awareness. • Deeper analytical collaboration with civilian experts. • Rapid dissemination of high-priority intelligence.
A.19	Simplify Technology Transfer Processes	<p>Streamlined procedures remove bureaucratic hurdles that slow the adaptation of defence-developed innovations for civilian use (or vice versa). Clear guidelines, reduced paperwork, and pre-approved licensing terms help ensure that beneficial technologies reach all relevant stakeholders quickly.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faster adoption of high-level security tools. • Reduced administrative burden and costs. • Enhanced collaboration with defence innovators. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Swift integration of commercial breakthroughs. • Less red tape in sharing R&D outcomes. • Efficient deployment of critical technologies.
A.20	Develop Unified Policy Frameworks	<p>Comprehensive policies define shared rules-of-engagement, reporting obligations, data handling standards, and escalation protocols. By covering both civilian and defence domains, unified frameworks create predictability, consistency, and a sense of joint commitment to safeguarding the national cyber landscape.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear compliance guidelines. • Transparent escalation pathways. • Stronger trust in national security measures. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unambiguous roles and responsibilities. • Seamless collaboration with civilian agencies. • Consistent cross-domain operational readiness.
A.21	Promote Cross-Sector Policy Dialogue	<p>Regular policy forums bring regulators, lawmakers, defence strategists, and corporate compliance officers together. They discuss emerging threats, refine legal frameworks, and coordinate on international norms. Consistent dialogue ensures that policies remain aligned with evolving technologies and adversary tactics.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creates a consistent legal framework. • Reduces regulatory confusion. • Ensures compliance without sacrificing privacy or operational flexibility. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harmonised policies enable smoother coordination with civilian entities. • Enhances incident response collaboration. • Ensures security measures across sectors reinforce each other.
A.22	Streamline Compliance Processes	<p>Aligned regulations and simplified audits reduce the administrative burden on organisations straddling both civilian and defence spheres. Unified compliance checklists and standardised reporting templates make it easier to meet security mandates efficiently, freeing resources for proactive threat defence.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced bureaucratic complexity. • Easier cross-sector collaboration. • More resources for innovation and security. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faster compliance turnaround. • Consistent standards across multiple agencies. • Enhanced focus on mission-critical operations.

A.23	Leverage International Best Practices	By studying frameworks like NATO cyber standards, ENISA guidelines, or ISO certifications, domestic stakeholders adopt proven methods from trusted allies. Incorporating global best practices accelerates learning, supports interoperability with international partners, and keeps local policies at the cutting edge of cybersecurity defence.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rapid adoption of established protocols. • Heightened global credibility and trust. • Streamlined collaboration with international allies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alignment with global security standards. • Enhanced cross-border operational coordination.
A.24	Cultural Exchange Initiatives	Informal gatherings, seminars, and team-building activities help civilian, and defence professionals understand each other's work cultures. This fosters mutual respect, eases tensions arising from different hierarchies or communication styles, and ensures everyone can collaborate smoothly under stress.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better understanding of defence protocols. • Improved communication with military counterparts. • Heightened team cohesion during joint operations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deeper insight into civilian workflows. • Reduced cultural barriers and misunderstandings. • Smoother integration in multi-agency cyber responses.
A.25	Develop Common Terminologies and Protocols	Agreeing on key terms, acronyms, severity scales, and escalation triggers eliminates confusion. Whether reporting an incident or discussing a vulnerability, all parties use a shared "language," speeding up decision-making and reducing the risk of misunderstandings during critical incidents.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced miscommunication in multi-agency operations. • Faster, more accurate incident reporting. • Streamlined collaboration with defence partners. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consistent vocabulary across various units. • Enhanced clarity when coordinating with civilians. • Decreased risk of delays or errors under pressure.
A.26	Trust-Building Activities	Long-term mentorships, collaborative research, and joint participation in professional associations allow relationships to deepen over time. As trust grows, stakeholders become more willing to share sensitive information, propose daring solutions, and rely on each other's judgment in high-stakes situations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced confidence in defence partnerships. • Willingness to share proprietary research. • Deeper cooperative efforts on strategic initiatives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved access to civilian expertise. • Greater openness to collaborative innovations. • Solidified bonds for high-stakes cyber operations.
A.27	Fast Reorganisation Programs	Implement procedures that allow rapid reallocation of cybersecurity tools, personnel, and expertise between civilian and defence sectors during emergencies. This ensures that when one sector faces resource shortages or complex threats, it can temporarily draw on the other's capabilities, maintaining robust protection of critical infrastructure under all conditions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Immediate access to skilled personnel. • Minimised service disruptions. • Agile response to escalating threats. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficient reallocation of specialised teams. • Flexible utilisation of civilian-focused resources. • Maintained readiness during large-scale incidents.

<p>A.28</p>	<p>Vulnerability and Threat Analysis Policies</p>	<p>Mandatory implementation of policies related to vulnerability and threat analysis ensures enterprises systematically identify and address risks. Regular audits evaluate the robustness of existing systems, uncover gaps, and assess the effectiveness of current cybersecurity measures. Based on these findings, organisations can develop tailored mitigation strategies that minimise risks and reduce potential impacts. These proactive policies not only strengthen an organisation's resilience but also foster a culture of continuous improvement in addressing evolving cyber threats.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proactive identification of systemic risks. • Targeted mitigation strategies to minimise impact. • Cultivation of a security-conscious organisational culture. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consistent security assessments across units. • Refined protocols for emerging threat landscapes. • Enhanced resilience through continuous risk analysis.
<p>A.29</p>	<p>Shared Funding and Resources</p>	<p>The defence sector often has significantly larger budgets allocated to cybersecurity compared to the civilian sector. However, both sectors rely on many of the same technologies and face similar threats. By pooling resources through shared funding initiatives, both civilian and defence organisations can access cutting-edge cybersecurity tools, research, and expertise. This will benefit both sectors by boosting cybersecurity resilience and innovation.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civilian industries can access advanced technologies and expertise typically reserved for defence agencies, leading to more innovation and stronger cybersecurity defences. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pooled resources can help optimise spending, reduce redundant efforts, and spur innovations that benefit both sectors, particularly in dual-use technologies.
<p>A.30</p>	<p>Long-Term Collaboration Agreements</p>	<p>These agreements can take the form of Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs), long-term contracts, or even treaties, depending on the scope and strategic importance. Such agreements outline the shared goals, expectations, and terms of collaboration, ensuring that both sectors stay committed to working together over the long term.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • These agreements ensure that collaboration persists even beyond individual political cycles or cybersecurity incidents, providing stability and long-term support for joint initiatives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having formal commitments helps lock in civilian contributions to defence cybersecurity efforts, ensuring sustained cooperation and preventing lapses due to shifting priorities.

A.31	Unified Threat Intelligence (TI) and Early Warning Systems	Both the civilian and defence sectors often have separate threat intelligence (TI) and early warning systems. Civilian agencies typically focus on economic, infrastructure, or corporate threats, while defence sectors focus on state-sponsored or national security-related cyber threats. By creating a unified early warning and threat intelligence system, these two sectors can combine their strengths to identify, assess, and respond to threats faster and more effectively.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Civilian companies and critical infrastructure operators can gain early insights into threats that may affect their operations, leading to faster and more coordinated defences. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unified threat intelligence ensures that military and defence operations are aware of broader cyber threats that could impact civilian infrastructure critical to defence activities, allowing them to be more proactive in national defence.
A.32	Cross-Sector Vulnerability Disclosure Mechanisms	Cross-sector vulnerability disclosure mechanisms help report and address cybersecurity vulnerabilities across civilian and defence sectors. They promote responsible disclosure by private companies, researchers, and government agencies.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Protect critical infrastructure such as energy grids, healthcare, and transportation. Create partnerships with private companies and researchers to enhance security. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure defence systems are secure from cyberattacks before vulnerabilities can be exploited. Joint civilian-defence teams address vulnerabilities with national security in mind.

Table 16 Potential areas for collaboration

Each initiative described above works toward a common goal: integrating civilian and defence efforts to create a cohesive, dynamic, and secure national cybersecurity environment. By combining operational measures, policy alignment, skill-building, innovation, and cultural understanding, these approaches collectively lay the foundation for enduring cyber resilience.

Focus Groups and Interview insights:

- During the focus groups, 16 initiatives were initially presented. Based on stakeholder feedback and comments, this number has now expanded to 32 initiatives, listed above as A1-A32. All these initiatives have been identified as important and provide valuable insights into enhancing collaboration.
- Notably, stakeholders from the defence sector (interviews), regulators (focus groups and interviews), and large businesses (focus groups and interviews) were highly active in proposing initiatives and made significant contributions to the report. In contrast, small businesses (focus groups) were less engaged, providing limited input, which resulted in a smaller contribution to the findings of this report.

Survey insights:

- Funding and training limitations persist across all sectors.
- Based on survey responses, the findings suggest a phased strategy for enhancing collaboration: short-term efforts focused on crisis management, real-time threat intelligence, and awareness campaigns; medium-term initiatives emphasising collaborative threat intelligence networks, public-private partnerships, and R&D; and long-term goals centred on innovation, harmonised frameworks, and cross-sector crisis management.
- Regional perspectives on these challenges vary significantly, confirming the need for location-specific approaches.

- Looking ahead, the community values comprehensive knowledge bases, best practices, and mapping tools, although sector-specific preferences—such as civilians leaning toward publications and defence favouring interactive maps—illustrate the importance of tailored solutions.
- Civilians excel in networking, partnerships, and training, while defence offers policy/regulatory expertise and infrastructure, and other stakeholders balance multiple contributions but require greater capacity in research and threat intelligence.
- Across all groups, access to shared resources and collaboration opportunities is crucial for sustained engagement, with recognition of contributions and regular updates on emerging threats seen as secondary.
- When it comes to preferred activities, joint cybersecurity projects and consistent information-sharing are widely endorsed, although civilians are more open to co-developing tools, whereas defence emphasises joint training and policy alignment.
- Building a resilient cybersecurity ecosystem demands strategies that address sector-specific strengths, leverage visual and data-driven platforms for knowledge-sharing, and balance immediate operational needs with long-term strategic investments in research, innovation, and harmonisation.
- By strengthening trust, communication, and engagement through concrete, action-oriented projects, diverse stakeholders can bridge existing gaps, align priorities, and achieve shared resilience goals across different regions.

A detailed analysis of the Survey can be found in **Appendix 6. Detailed analysis of the survey.**

3 Recommendations

The recommendations in this section are grouped into **three categories: short-term** (less than 2 years), **medium-term** (2–5 years), and **long-term** (5+ years). This categorisation is based on insights we structured based on focus groups and interviews, which highlighted the varying urgency and feasibility of proposed actions. By structuring the recommendations in this way, we aim to provide a clear and **actionable foundation for the roadmap** that addresses immediate needs, builds on early successes, and sets the foundation for sustained collaboration over time.

3.1 Short-term strategies (less than 2 years)

To ensure clarity and focus, the short-term strategies have been organised into three thematic sections:

- **Information-sharing mechanisms:** Immediate actions to establish secure and efficient channels for the exchange of cyber threat intelligence between the civilian and defence sectors.
- **Joint operational readiness:** Practical steps to prepare both sectors for coordinated responses to
- **Governance and framework alignment:** Foundational efforts to create common protocols, shared terminology, and initial governance frameworks to facilitate collaboration.

The following short-term strategies are proposed:

3.1.1 Information sharing mechanisms

S.1 **Real-time threat intelligence sharing platforms (Linked to A.3 – Potential areas for collaboration).** Establish secure digital platforms that enable the immediate exchange of verified cyber threat data between civilian agencies and defence bodies.

Objective	Build a secure digital platform that allows approved users to share cyber threat data—malicious IP addresses, evolving malware signatures, newly discovered vulnerabilities—in near real-time.
Recommendation on Implementation steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop a centralised, secure platform with robust access controls and encryption standards. 2. Standardise data formats and protocols to enable seamless sharing and integration. 3. Conduct training sessions for approved users to maximise platform usage and compliance. 4. Establish a governance team to monitor usage, maintain the platform, and address evolving security needs.
Expected outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accelerated incorporation of threat intelligence into protective measures. • A secure and reliable system for real-time threat intelligence exchange.

S.2 **Collaborative threat intelligence networks (Linked to A.18 – Potential areas for collaboration).** Launch pilot networks allowing analysts from both sectors to share information (indicators of

compromise, vulnerabilities, and emerging threats), tools, and research, building trust and teamwork.

Objective	Establish longer-term alliances (or partnership) among analysts and cybersecurity experts to routinely share datasets, research findings, and toolkits, fostering a community of trust and collaboration.
Recommendation on Implementation steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Form alliances among key analysts from both civilian and defence sectors, creating a clear framework for collaboration. 2. Organise regular virtual and in-person meetings to maintain ongoing dialogue and build rapport. 3. Develop and maintain shared repositories for research, tools, and critical updates. 4. Establish feedback mechanisms to evaluate network effectiveness and refine collaboration practices.
Expected outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A sustainable and trusted community of cybersecurity practitioners. • Improved dissemination of critical updates and collaborative research.

3.1.2 Joint operational readiness

S.3 **Joint Cyber incident response teams (Linked to A.1 – Potential areas for collaboration).** From small, agile multi-stakeholder teams that can be activated during cyber incidents, ensuring coordinated containment, mitigation, and restoration efforts.

Objective	Form agile teams from both civilian and defence groups to coordinate actions during cyberattacks.
Recommendation on Implementation steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop realistic and relevant cybersecurity scenarios based on current threat intelligence. 2. Involve stakeholders from both sectors to design and execute joint drills. 3. Collect data and feedback from participants to identify coordination gaps and lessons learned. 4. Update operational protocols and training materials based on drill outcomes.
Expected outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greater readiness for handling joint cybersecurity incidents. • Improved teamwork between civilian and defence professionals.

3.1.3 Governance and framework alignment

S.4 **Develop common terminologies and protocols (Linked to A.25 – Potential areas for collaboration).** Establish a baseline lexicon and standardised operating procedures to reduce confusion and ensure consistent communication across civilian and defence groups.

<p>Objective</p>	<p>Create a shared dictionary (language) and unified operational procedures so that everyone in civilian and defence groups understands each other clearly and streamline collaboration.</p>
<p>Recommendation on Implementation steps</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Assemble a working group of civilian and defence representatives to identify critical terms and processes. 2. Draft and validate a shared lexicon and set of standard operating procedures (SOPs). 3. Incorporate these into training and policy documents for both sectors. 4. Review and update the terminology and SOPs regularly to reflect evolving challenges.
<p>Expected outcome</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear and consistent communication during joint operations. • Reduced errors and delays caused by terminology discrepancies.

S.5 Simplify technology transfer processes (Linked to A.19 – Potential areas for collaboration).

Streamline procedures for transferring relevant technologies and best practices from defence R&D to civilian markets, lowering barriers to practical collaboration.

<p>Objective</p>	<p>Make it easier to bring innovative defence technologies to the civilian market, speeding up collaboration and technology use.</p>
<p>Recommendation on Implementation steps</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify key technologies and innovations in defence R&D with dual-use potential. 2. Develop a standardised framework for evaluating and approving technology transfers. 3. Establish dedicated liaison teams to facilitate communication and address bureaucratic hurdles. 4. Pilot the framework with selected technologies to refine processes and identify bottlenecks.
<p>Expected outcome</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accelerated adoption of cutting-edge defence innovations in civilian cybersecurity. • Stronger collaboration and knowledge-sharing between R&D entities in both sectors, and increased efficiency and reduced delays in technology transfer processes.

S.6 Cross-sector Cybersecurity workshops (Linked to A.15 – Potential areas for collaboration).
 Host regular, scenario-based workshops that bring together civilian IT professionals and military cyber units to foster trust, enhance communication, and identify interoperability gaps.

Objective	Host workshops where civilian IT and military cyber experts come together to build trust, share ideas, and find ways to work better together.
Recommendation on Implementation steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop workshop themes and scenarios relevant to both civilian and defence cybersecurity challenges. 2. Identify and invite participants from both sectors, ensuring balanced representation. 3. Facilitate interactive sessions focused on practical exercises, case studies, and open dialogue. 4. Collect participant feedback to continuously improve workshop content and execution.
Expected outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthened trust and collaboration between civilian and defence cybersecurity professionals. • Improved understanding of each sector’s priorities, constraints, and operational methods.

3.2 Medium-term strategies (2–5 years)

To ensure clarity and focus, the medium-term strategies have also been organised into three thematic sections:

1. **Integrated capacity building and skills development:** Strategies aimed at enhancing the skills and expertise of professionals in both civilian and defence sectors through joint training programs, exchange initiatives, and capacity-building efforts.
2. **Enhanced governance and policy harmonisation:** Efforts to align policies, protocols, and governance structures across the civilian and defence sectors.
3. **Shared testing and evaluation platforms:** Initiatives to create common platforms for testing and evaluating cybersecurity solutions, enabling joint assessments, and fostering trust between sectors. These platforms serve as a foundation for innovation and preparedness.

The following medium-term strategies are proposed:

3.2.1 Integrated capacity building and skills development

M.1 Joint Cybersecurity training programs (Linked to A.4 – Potential areas for collaboration).
 Develop advanced training initiatives where civilian and defence personnel learn side-by-side, simulating joint response operations and fostering mutual understanding.

Objective	Train civilian and defence teams side-by-side to simulate real-life cyber threats, improving teamwork and mutual understanding.
Recommendation on Implementation steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Design training curricula that incorporate both civilian and military perspectives. 2. Conduct regular simulations of joint cyber incidents to reinforce operational coordination. 3. Collaborate with academic and training institutions to accredit the programs. 4. Evaluate program outcomes and refine curricula to address gaps identified during training sessions.
Expected outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthened interpersonal and operational trust between sectors. • A skilled workforce prepared for integrated cybersecurity operations.

M.2 Exchange programs (Linked to A.17 – Potential areas for collaboration). Facilitate temporary staff rotations and secondments between civilian cyber agencies and military cyber command units to deepen organisational knowledge exchange.

Objective	Allow staff from civilian and defence organisations to temporarily swap roles, learning from each other’s work environments and building stronger connections.
Recommendation on Implementation steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establish agreements outlining the terms and objectives of exchanges. 2. Identify and train participants for effective role adaptation during their secondments. 3. Create feedback loops to document lessons learned. 4. Incorporate feedback into exchange program refinement and adjust future rotations.
Expected outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced understanding of each sector’s workflows, constraints, and best practices. • Improved communication and mutual respect between civilian and defence personnel.

M.3 Fast reorganisation programs (Linked to A.27 – Potential areas for collaboration): Once foundational trust and governance are in place, implement procedures for swiftly reallocating cybersecurity resources, personnel, and tools between civilian and defence sectors during emergencies. This ensures that sudden capability gaps can be filled promptly, maintaining robust protection against emerging threats.

Objective	Set up systems that quickly move resources, tools, and people between civilian and defence sectors during cyber emergencies to close any gaps.
Recommendation on Implementation steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop clear protocols for resource mobilisation and reallocation during crises. 2. Establish a centralised resource directory to track available personnel, tools, and expertise. 3. Conduct drills to test resource reallocation processes under simulated emergency conditions. 4. Address logistical challenges and refine protocols based on drill outcomes.
Expected outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced response times during cyber crises. • Strengthened resilience against sudden capability gaps.

3.2.2 Enhanced governance and policy harmonization

M.4 **Develop unified policy frameworks (Linked to A.20 – Potential areas for collaboration).** Draft overarching cyber policy standards to which both civilian and defence stakeholders adhere, ensuring compatibility in rules of engagement and incident escalation.

Objective	Create clear, overarching rules that both civilian and defence groups can follow to ensure smooth and aligned operations during cybersecurity incidents.
Recommendation on Implementation steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Convene a multi-sector working group to draft the framework, ensuring balanced representation. 2. Align the framework with existing international standards and agreements to ensure compatibility. 3. Pilot the framework in small-scale scenarios and evaluate its effectiveness. 4. Refine the framework based on pilot findings and disseminate it broadly across sectors.
Expected outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced friction in joint operations. • A cohesive policy environment supporting collaboration.

M.5 **Public-private Cybersecurity partnerships (Linked to A.6 – Potential areas for collaboration).** Involve private-sector cybersecurity firms as strategic partners to infuse cutting-edge innovation, bolster public trust, and rapidly adopt best practices.

Objective	Involve private cybersecurity companies as key partners to bring innovation, build public trust, and quickly adopt new practices.
Recommendation on Implementation steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify leading private-sector firms with expertise in cybersecurity innovation and establish formal partnerships. 2. Develop collaborative research initiatives focusing on shared cybersecurity challenges. 3. Facilitate regular workshops to share findings and align priorities between public and private stakeholders. 4. Create channels for private-sector insights to be incorporated into national cybersecurity policies and practices.
Expected outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accelerated technology transfer and innovation. • A pipeline of advanced tools and solutions to address evolving cyber threats.

3.2.3 Shared testing and evaluation platforms

M.6 National Cybersecurity simulations (Linked to A.10 – Potential areas for collaboration).

Conduct annual joint exercises that stress-test collective response capabilities to complex cyber-attacks, refining strategies and identifying policy or resource shortfalls.

Objective	Hold annual exercises to test how civilian and defence teams respond to large cyberattacks, improving strategies and identifying weak points.
Recommendation on Implementation steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop detailed scenarios simulating large-scale, multi-vector cyber-attacks. 2. Engage diverse participants, including civilian, defence, and private-sector stakeholders. 3. Use structured post-simulation debriefs to identify capability gaps and areas for improvement. 4. Publish actionable recommendations based on simulation findings to inform future policy and preparedness efforts.
Expected outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthened national readiness for complex cyber threats. • Clearer understanding of resource needs and policy adjustments.

M.7 Integrated crisis management frameworks (Linked to A.5 – Potential areas for collaboration).

Align crisis management protocols so that civilian and defence entities can seamlessly coordinate response actions and ensure unified messaging during cyber crises.

Objective	Align crisis management plans so civilian and defence groups can respond together seamlessly and communicate effectively during cyber crises.
Recommendation on Implementation steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Conduct a comprehensive review of existing crisis management frameworks in both civilian and defence sectors. 2. Develop a unified protocol with input from all relevant stakeholders. 3. Pilot the integrated framework in simulated crisis scenarios and adjust based on outcomes. 4. Disseminate the framework widely with accompanying training programs for stakeholders.
Expected outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Streamlined crisis response coordination between civilian and defence entities. • Reduced operational delays and duplication of efforts in high-pressure situations.

3.3 Long-term strategies (5+ years)

Long-term strategies focus on creating a sustainable and resilient ecosystem for civilian-defence collaboration. To ensure clarity and focus, the long-term strategies have been organised into two thematic sections:

1. **Strategic innovation and sustainable collaboration:** This category focuses on fostering continuous technological advancements and establishing permanent structures for research, innovation, and knowledge-sharing between the civilian and defence sectors. It emphasises long-term partnerships and co-development of solutions to address evolving cybersecurity challenges.
2. **Institutionalised governance and international integration:** Efforts under this theme aim to create robust institutional frameworks and align governance structures that facilitate seamless collaboration between sectors. Additionally, it focuses on positioning the EU as a global leader in cybersecurity by aligning with international standards and fostering cross-border cooperation.

The following long-term strategies are proposed:

3.3.1 Strategic innovation and sustainable collaboration

- L.1 **Create Cybersecurity innovation hubs (Linked to A.12 - Potential areas for collaboration).**
Establish permanent innovation centres to accelerate R&D on dual-use cybersecurity technologies, bringing together academia, industry, civilian agencies, and defence researchers.

<p>Objective</p>	<p>Develop permanent centers where civilian researchers, defence experts, and private-sector innovators collaborate to co-develop advanced cybersecurity solutions.</p>
<p>Recommendation on Implementation steps</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Secure funding through public-private partnerships and EU grants to establish the hubs. 2. Recruit multidisciplinary teams of researchers, practitioners, and policymakers. 3. Launch pilot projects focusing on dual-use technologies. 4. Expand the hubs based on the success of initial projects, incorporating lessons learned.
<p>Expected outcome</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous development of cutting-edge cybersecurity solutions. • Stronger ties between civilian, defence, and private-sector stakeholders.

L.2 Launch joint Cybersecurity R&D initiatives (Linked to A.13 – Potential areas for collaboration).
 Fund multi-year research programs focusing on advanced areas like quantum-resistant encryption, AI-driven threat detection, and secure-by-design hardware.

<p>Objective</p>	<p>Create detailed, forward-looking roadmaps to guide the development and adoption of cybersecurity technologies over the next decade.</p>
<p>Recommendation on Implementation steps</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Conduct foresight studies to identify emerging threats and technological trends. 2. Collaborate with stakeholders to draft technology roadmaps that align with national and EU priorities. 3. Regularly update the roadmaps to reflect new developments and lessons learned. 4. Monitor the implementation of roadmap recommendations and adjust priorities as needed.
<p>Expected outcome</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved resource allocation and strategic planning. • Strong alignment between civilian and defence research initiatives.

3.3.2 Institutionalised governance and international integration

L.3 Harmonised Cybersecurity framework (Linked to A.7 – Potential areas for collaboration).
 Finalise and adopt a nation-wide framework that sets uniform standards, ensuring that civilian and defence efforts are not only aligned internally but also recognised internationally.

<p>Objective</p>	<p>Align cybersecurity regulations across civilian and defence sectors to ensure consistency and facilitate joint operations.</p>
<p>Recommendation on Implementation steps</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Review existing regulations to identify inconsistencies and gaps. 2. Establish a multi-sector task force to draft harmonised frameworks. 3. Pilot the frameworks in select regions to identify potential issues. 4. Roll out the frameworks at the national and EU levels, incorporating stakeholder feedback.
<p>Expected outcome</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Streamlined regulatory processes and reduced operational friction. • Stronger legal and operational cohesion across sectors.

L.4 Leverage international best practices (Linked to A.23 – Potential areas for collaboration).
 Integrate lessons from allied nations and international cybersecurity bodies, positioning the country as a global leader in civil-defence cyber cooperation.

<p>Objective</p>	<p>Integrate lessons from allied nations and international cybersecurity bodies, positioning the country as a global leader in civil-defence cyber cooperation.</p>
<p>Recommendation on Implementation steps</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Analyse successful cybersecurity initiatives from allied nations and international bodies. 2. Adapt and integrate these best practices into national cybersecurity strategies. 3. Establish bilateral agreements to facilitate knowledge-sharing and joint training exercises. 4. Develop metrics to evaluate the effectiveness of implemented practices and refine as necessary.
<p>Expected outcome</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced national cybersecurity strategies informed by proven international practices. • Increased interoperability with international allies.

L.5 Cultural exchange initiatives (Linked to A.24 – Potential areas for collaboration). Continuously sponsor forums, seminars, and community-building events that break down cultural barriers between sectors, emphasising shared mission over organisational differences.

Objective	Continuously sponsor forums, seminars, and community-building events that break down cultural barriers between sectors, emphasising shared missions over organisational differences.
Recommendation on Implementation steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop an annual schedule of events tailored to address specific cultural gaps. 2. Facilitate participation from diverse stakeholders, including civilian, defence, and private-sector representatives. 3. Incorporate interactive activities, such as scenario-based workshops, to foster collaboration. 4. Collect feedback from participants to improve future events and maximise impact.
Expected outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long-term relationships that facilitate smoother collaboration. • A stronger sense of shared mission and mutual respect.

L.6 Trust-building activities (Linked to A.26 – Potential areas for collaboration). Regular joint projects, long-term mentorship programs, and executive-level retreats to ensure sustained personal relationships and mutual confidence.

Objective	Establish regular joint projects, long-term mentorship programs, and executive-level retreats to ensure sustained personal relationships and mutual confidence.
Recommendation on Implementation steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify key stakeholders and leaders to participate in trust-building initiatives. 2. Develop joint projects and mentorship programs focused on shared objectives. 3. Organise annual retreats for high-level executives to align on strategic goals. 4. Evaluate the impact of these initiatives through surveys and interviews, refining programs as needed.
Expected outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthened personal relationships between key leaders in civilian and defence sectors. • A foundation of trust that enhances operational effectiveness.

4 Conclusions and Next Steps

The needs assessment of civilian–defence cybersecurity collaboration was conducted through **three streams** of consultations involving **Interviews** of selected professionals, **Focus Groups**, and a **Survey** sent to the COcyber community. A literature review brought fundamental knowledge that we could validate during those consultations.

This study has highlighted the critical need for enhanced and strengthened collaboration between the civilian and defence sectors. **Eight (8) main arguments were identified for structured and long-lasting participation and collaboration** between cybersecurity civilian and defence spheres.

Those include the **Fragmentation of cybersecurity efforts** amplified by the increasing complexity of cyber threats, the shared reliance on critical infrastructure, and by **the lack of aligned responses to incidents. It also involves the lack of or limited information-sharing, lack of awareness capacity, lack of dual-use technologies, lack of coordinated cybersecurity policies, lack of cross-pollination of ideas and best practices, lack of cutting-edge innovation and cultural differences.**

Based on literature review, focus groups and interview insights, by identifying gaps, challenges, and opportunities in areas such as information sharing, joint operational readiness, governance, and cultural alignment, we reflected on a total of 32 **recommendations for improved collaboration**, outlining the purpose, the mechanisms by which it would operate, and the benefits each would bring to strengthening collaboration between civilian and defence cybersecurity spheres.

Based on Survey insights it is essential to:

- Tailor collaboration strategies to address sector-specific concerns and strengths.
- Create targeted, visual, and data-driven platforms that facilitate knowledge-sharing and situational awareness.
- Balance short-term operational needs with long-term strategic efforts focused on research, innovation, and harmonisation of approaches.
- Strengthen trust and foster communication channels through consistent engagement, shared resources, and concrete, action-oriented projects.

In conclusion, the proposed recommendations outlined **strategies to strengthen cybersecurity collaboration** between civilian and defence sectors. The foundation for roadmap is phased to ensure progressive development and long-term sustainability:

- **Short-Term (less than 2 Years): Building trust and operational synergy.**
 - Quickly set up basic operational collaboration: rapid threat intelligence exchange, joint incident response teams, and cross-sector workshops.
 - Begin simplifying technology transfer processes and standardising protocols to enable smooth early-stage cooperation.
- **Medium-Term (2–5 Years): Focus on capacity building and governance harmonisation to strengthen the ecosystem further.**
 - Conduct joint cybersecurity training, run national simulations, and form public-private partnerships to raise professional standards and strengthen collective response capabilities.
 - Develop unified policy frameworks and integrated crisis management strategies.

- **Long-Term (3–5+ Years): Ensure sustainable innovation, institutional alignment, and global leadership.**
 - Institutionalise these collaborative efforts through long-term governance frameworks, create permanent innovation hubs, integrate R&D efforts for advanced technology (e.g., AI, quantum security), and harmonise national efforts with international best practices.

Key takeaways include the recognition **that trust, communication, and shared objectives are paramount for success**. Building lasting relationships, harmonising policies, and fostering innovation are not only operational imperatives but strategic priorities for creating a unified cybersecurity front.

Moving forward, **implementation will require coordinated efforts, resource allocation, and ongoing evaluation** to ensure the proposed measures achieve their intended impact. While this report provides a background for a clear roadmap, but its success depends on the commitment and collaboration of all stakeholders involved.

In conclusion, **bridging the civilian–defence divide is not just a necessity but an opportunity to redefine how cybersecurity challenges are addressed at national, regional, and international levels**. By acting on these recommendations, the EU can position itself as a global leader in cybersecurity while safeguarding critical infrastructures and the digital resilience of its societies.

The next steps build on the core pillars identified in the needs assessment: **enhanced coordination, stakeholder engagement, exchange and collaboration mechanisms, and fostering synergies**. These actions will ensure that the insights gathered from surveys, focus groups, and interviews translate into a **structured, impactful, and sustainable collaboration** between civilian and defence cybersecurity stakeholders.

Advancing enhanced coordination (T2.3, T3.1, T3.2, T3.3)

- The findings of this report on needs assessment will directly inform the **COcyber roadmap and coordination activities (T2.3)**, establishing a clear framework for long-term collaboration.
- The **Cybersecurity Observatory (T3.1)** will integrate the identified needs from civilian and defence sectors, providing continuous monitoring of the evolving civilian–defence cybersecurity landscape.

Improving exchange and coordination mechanisms (T4.1, T4.2)

- The **best practices and case studies for enhanced cooperation (T4.1)** will be compiled based on the feedback received from three streams of needs assessment analysis, leveraging real-world insights from successful cybersecurity collaborations.
- The **exchange of know-how and information-sharing activities (T4.2)** will be partially guided by the recommendations from the needs assessment analysis and further expanded to ensure that identified coordination challenges—such as fragmentation and limited information sharing—are systematically addressed.

Strengthening stakeholder engagement (T5.4)

- The insights gathered from the **451 identified stakeholders** will help in guiding targeted engagement initiatives, ensuring active participation from all relevant actors.
- The **COcyber ambassador programme (T5.4)** will be expanded to enhance outreach and advocacy, fostering stronger ties between key cybersecurity stakeholders. For example, based on

the outcomes of D2.2, additional efforts will be required to enhance SME involvement, addressing their previously limited contribution to the collaboration framework.

Fostering synergies between COcyber and other initiatives (T6.1, T6.3)

- **Synergies with existing initiatives (T6.1)** will be actively pursued, ensuring alignment with broader European cybersecurity efforts such as ECYBRIDGE and other cross-sector initiatives.
- **The COcyber sustainability strategy (T6.3)** will incorporate the insights from this report to ensure that collaboration efforts continue beyond the project's duration.

The findings of the needs assessment analysis will directly shape COcyber's roadmap, strengthening long-term collaboration and coordination mechanisms. Identified needs will be integrated into the Cybersecurity Observatory for continuous monitoring, while best practices and case studies will guide cooperation strategies. Targeted stakeholder engagement will be reinforced through the COcyber Ambassador programme, with particular attention to increasing SME involvement. By translating strategic insights into concrete actions, COcyber will enhance cybersecurity resilience and ensure sustainable civilian-defence collaboration beyond the project's duration.